

Polifonia: a digital harmoniser for musical heritage knowledge, H2020

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3	KCL	KING'S COLLEGE LONDON	United Kingdom
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5	MiC	MINISTERIO DELLA CULTURA	Italy
6	CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	France
	SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITE (LinkedTP)	France
7	CNAM	CONSERVATOIRE NATIONAL DES ARTS ET METIERS	France
8	NISV	STICHTING NEDERLANDS INSTITUUT VOOR BEELD EN GELUID	Netherlands
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Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars, and citizens will be able to navigate, explore, and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoire, reportage, news, biographies, reviews), different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an ecosystem of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Hence their development is guided by, and continuously intertwined with, experiments and validations performed in real-world settings, identified by musical heritage stakeholders (both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters) such as cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive Summary

The landscape of music ontologies to represent music metadata, content, and contextual information has seen several contributions in recent years, both in the audio and symbolic domains. Ontologies are necessary to generate semantically rich Music Knowledge Graphs that can describe the complexity and the diversity of music across different perspectives and domains, to serve various applications in information retrieval, digital humanities. Together with the ability to connect different sources of music data, this brings several benefits – from preserving our musical heritage on the Web to enabling scholars to discover new knowledge, such as unknown relations (influences, similarities), contributing novel methodologies for computational analyses, and completing missing artefacts (e.g. an unfinished composition). To achieve this vision – which is central to Polifonia, it is necessary that music ontologies can cover a diversified range of requirements, while potentially supporting future demands as extensions, and enabling their interoperability in a modular fashion (e.g. seamlessly using 2 or more ontologies).

However, the requirements and context of the Polifonia project, in addition to evidence collected through systematic surveys, demonstrated that current music ontologies lack interoperability, and are insufficient for representing music history and the cultural heritage context in which it was generated. Not only does this hampers the aforementioned vision, but also risks the propagation of recency and cultural biases to downstream applications.

To address this challenge and lay down the basis to the Music Web vision, this deliverable presents the first stable version of the Polifonia Ontology Network (PON) – a collection of ontologies for music cultural heritage, centred around four foundational modules: Music Meta (metadata), Representation (content), Source (provenance) and Instrument (cultural objects). We designed PON with a strong accent on cultural stakeholder requirements, collected from user stories and formulated as competency questions (CQs). Given the high number of stakeholders and the heterogeneity in domain expertise, we also contributed a toolkit using Language Models to support knowledge engineers in generating, validating, and analysing CQs. Following the application of our toolkit on Polifonia's requirements, we also release our high-quality competency questions in the PolifoniaCQ dataset.

This deliverable also reports current and future use of these resources by our internal project pilots, early adopters in the music industry and cultural heritage sectors, and opportunities for the Semantic Web and Music Information Retrieval communities. In addition, we provide an overview of how PON is being used in Polifonia, the Knowledge Graphs that have been developed so far, and our plans for future extensions and integration. The deliverable concludes with a use case showing how PON can support contributions in computational creativity, and enable novel workflows and pipelines for the exploration of chord datasets.

From our pilots, we highlight the ChoCo and Harmory knowledge graphs from INTERLINK, using our ontologies to integrate harmonic data from various datasets, semantically describing their content, similarity, and structural segmentation. Synergies across pilots have enabled the reuse of INTERLINK technologies in the ACCESS pilot (mapping harmony to haptic signals for hearing-impaired listeners), as well as ontological and software support for the TUNES pilot (modelling melodic patterns). In parallel, our ontologies encoding music theories are enabling the formal analysis of symbolic music in the TONALITIES pilot, providing complementary interpretations for the identification of cadences in a fully explainable way. PON's coverage of contextual music knowledge is also contributing to the semantic description of musical instruments, starting from their general and abstract properties (materials, builders, locations, maintenance, etc.) and specialising into ORGANS and BELLS for the respective pilots. Finally, a central module of PON – the Music Meta ontology, is being used across all pilots in Polifonia, and is now under evaluation and extension for potential reuse by our music industry and cultural heritage partners (Polifonia Stakeholder Network). Notably, while addressing Polifonia requirements in alignment with other relevant contributions (Music Ontology, DOREMUS, Wikidata), Music Meta is opening up new opportunities to address issues related to metadata attribution and copyright management.

Document History

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V0.2	10/06/2023	Second version with Polifonia Ontology Network	KCL
V0.3	20/07/2023	Extended version with updated survey	KCL
V0.4	07/08/2023	Amendments by co-authors	KCL, UniBo, OU
V0.5	14/08/2023	Amendments by co-authors	NISV
V0.6	15/08/2023	Amendments by co-authors	KNAW, CRNS, CNAM
V0.7	18/08/2023	Version submitted to reviewers	KCL
V0.8	27/09/2023	Revisions and integrations	KCL
V1.0	02/10/2023	Final	KCL

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1 Introduction

Musical heritage encompasses a diversity of human expressions and experiences leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to describe, connect, and preserve [1]. In Europe, music cultural heritage developed through varied sources: musical contents and objects (such as tunes, scores, melodies, notations, recordings, etc.¹) linked to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, instruments, etc.) but also to their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people with diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and facts expressed in different styles and perspectives (memoire, reportage, news, biographies, reviews) in different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German) and across centuries [2]. This diversity creates unique opportunities as well as challenges for researchers and practitioners attempting to study and preserve music heritage.

In the Polifonia project, various memory institutions, museums, music archives, scholars, commercial organisations, and citizens ask questions (e.g. “Which tunes share melodic patterns and geographical origin?”; “How do libretto and music relate, e.g. in describing an emotion?”; “Can we trace the evolution of tonality and transition from modal to tonal?”) across these multi-perspective and multi-modal sources. This demands the integration of musicological (notes, chords, modes, theories), historical (events, persons, places, objects) and archival/preservation (metadata, descriptors) data and perspectives. The four cultural institutions involved in the project (CNAM, NISV, MiC, KNAW), with the 10 pilots cover a large variety and number of requirements. Ontologies and knowledge graphs (KGs) have the potential to overcome these challenges, and shed light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new music history knowledge that was previously overlooked and therefore missing [3, 4]. This is still a timely vision to pursue, given the relevance of Linked Open Data (LOD) as a format to share data on the Web, given that more and more websites have started to embed *structured data* into their HTML pages in the past 20 years². Structured data often follows markup standards such as Microdata, RDFa, and Microformats, and JSON-LD – with the latter being the most used. For example, the Web Data Commons project found that 47% of HTML pages on the Web provides structured data³. Given the extensive number of Web resources and services providing music-related data – such as MusicBrainz, Discogs, Wikidata, Genius, Spotify APIs to name a few, this easily translates to the music domain – where there is a plethora of music data represented in several non-interchangeable formats, and LOD is deemed a lingua franca in several Cultural Heritage projects.

Various ontologies and knowledge engineering methods have been proposed and applied to music industry and cultural heritage [5, 6]. For example, the Music Ontology [5] and DOREMUS [7] provide models to describe music metadata with a focus on discographic and classical music, respectively. Although these ontologies cover some aspects of musical heritage interest, they are individually insufficient to overcome the challenge of integrating the notation, metadata, and historical contexts needed for multi-perspective cultural analyses; thus leaving questions about the relationship between musical theory (melodies, tonalities, chords) and culture (historical events, architecture, geography) unanswered. To date, no available ontological framework integrates music metadata, notation, annotation, source provenance, and cultural heritage object descriptions. To the best of our knowledge, no toolkits exist to support knowledge engineering tasks around the lifecycle of competency questions, which is a central project requirement given the large number of variety of stakeholders, pilots and questions.

In sum, **two main research problems** emerged from our work in WP2: (i) current music ontologies have very specific scope (genre, style, dataset, target users, etc.) and they rarely focus on their *composability* and *interoperability*⁴ (c.f. Sections 3.3 and 3.2 for evidence of impact and reuse from our survey and stakeholders); (ii) designing large

¹Musical objects are intended as musical artefacts, such as scores and recording. For notation, instead, we refer to a type of encoding that can describe atomic musical elements, which in turn can be found explicitly in a score, or be the object of an analysis/annotation.

²<http://webdatacommons.org/structureddata/>

³Statistics were extracted from 1.5 billion HTML pages out of the 3.15 billion pages contained in the crawl. For more info, we refer to <http://webdatacommons.org/structureddata/2022-12/stats/stats.html>

⁴Here, intended as the ability to seamlessly use 2 or more ontologies in a modular fashion, without introducing inconsistencies.

ontology networks with the direct involvement of various domain experts (musicologists, archivists, music analysts, data engineers, etc.) is a *complex task* requiring the extension of current knowledge engineering methodologies, in terms of supporting tools and frameworks. In the following sections, we elaborate on the aforementioned research problems and provide pointers to relevant contributions to motivate our work.

1.1 The landscape of music ontologies

Ontologies play a fundamental role in the representation and management of knowledge, by providing common vocabularies to describe resources and queries. In the cultural heritage domain, there have been several efforts in this direction, such as the ArCo ontology, which pertains to the Italian cultural heritage [6], as well as others [4, 8]. Several ontologies exist in the music domain for addressing diverse music-related applications, dealing with both symbolic notations and audio signals at different levels of specificity. MusoW⁵ is a catalogue that indexes online music resources, including ontologies and knowledge graphs. Here, we focus on music ontologies and categorise them according to their reference domain: (i) metadata; (ii) music theory; (iii) music notation; and (iv) audio features.

Multiple ontologies exist for describing high-level music-related metadata, with the Music Ontology [5] and DOREMUS Ontology [9] being the most renowned. The MUSO Ontology [10] was proposed to model musical concepts of the Finnish National Library. Other models focus on specific metadata: the Performed Music Ontology⁶ specialises on performances, while the OnVIE Ontology [11] describes mediums of performances. Similarly, the Musical Instrument Taxonomies [12] model instruments conceptually and terminologically, while the Smart Music Instrument Ontology [13] covers sensors and components of instruments within the realm of the Internet of Musical Things [14].

Some ontologies describe different elements ascribable to *music theory*. The Music Theory Ontology (MTO) [15] covers theoretical concepts of music theory, while the Functional Harmony Ontology analyses harmonic sequences through reasoning. The Chord Ontology, Tonality Ontology, and Temperament Ontology [16] cover chords, tonal content, and instrument tuning, respectively.

Ontologies have also attempted to describe *musical notation*. For instance, the MIDI Linked Data Cloud [17] proposes a way to connect symbolic music descriptions that are encoded in the MIDI format. Meanwhile, the CHARM ontology [18] is focused on representing musical structures. The Music Theory Ontology (MTO) [15] aims to capture the theoretical concepts related to music compositions, while the Music Score Ontology (Music OWL) [19] and the Music Annotation Ontology [20] represent the content of a music score.

Other works focus on audio signals or the procedures used to produce them. For example, The Audio Features Ontology [21], The Studio Ontology [22], and The Audio Effects Ontology [23] are dedicated to describing different aspects of audio production. The Computational Analysis of the Live Music Archive (CALMA) [24] project aims to link metadata of music tracks with computational analyses of recordings, through feature extraction, clustering, and classification. Additionally, ontologies have been used to model listeners' habits and music tastes, as well as similarities between different musical pieces [25, 26, 27, 28]. For a more detailed overview of current music ontologies, we refer to D2.1 [29].

Despite the numerous contributions, the scope of these ontologies is often too specific or ingrained in a genre, style, historical period – often addressing individual music stakeholders and/or datasets. Several ontologies were also developed independently, with little coordination across relevant contributions. In turn, this often hampers reuse and extension, while jeopardising interoperability – an essential requirement for the integration of music datasets [30].

1.2 Current challenges in music ontologies: the example of music metadata

As an example, let us consider a common scenario: a music analyst, a computational musicologist, a music librarian, and a data engineer who are working on a joint project. They need to contribute data from various musical sources, ranging from music libraries, annotated corpora and tune books, to audiovisual archives, radio broadcasts, and

⁵<https://projects.dharc.unibo.it/musow/>

⁶<https://performedmusicontology.org/>

music catalogues. All data is eventually merged/aggregated as interconnected corpora, and linked to online music databases (e.g. MusicBrainz, Discogs) and knowledge bases (e.g. Wikidata). This creates opportunities to link cultural heritage artefacts to music industry data (streaming services, music professionals, etc.) and viceversa.

This plot subsumes a recurring challenge that is common to musical heritage projects [2]. Besides the individual requirements of each stakeholder – possibly rooted in different music genres, periods and datasets, a fundamental requirement is the interoperability of music metadata.

Music metadata (alias bibliographic, or documentary music data) is used to consistently identify and describe musical works, their artists, recordings, and performances. For music industry, it allows for efficient management and distribution of music, which facilitate search and recommendation [31]. When metadata is accurate, it ensures that artists receive proper credit and compensation [32]. For musical heritage, metadata allows for the preservation and dissemination of musical works and traditions, but also aid in the research and study of music history and culture [33]. When integrating both views, metadata can help to promote diversity and inclusivity in the music industry by highlighting lesser-known genres and artists, while integrating information and artefacts of cultural interest [34].

Hence, a model that can consistently describe metadata is highly desirable – as it enables linking entities and concepts from various datasets (e.g. a composer is linked to a tune that has no authors in another collection). To achieve interoperability, one possibility akin to [35] is to let stakeholders design their own domain-specific ontologies, then use alignment algorithms to find connections between them (e.g. `MusicalWork` and `Composition` referring to the same concept). However, this approach comes with three major drawbacks: (i) ontology alignment is error-prone, hence links would still require manual inspection; (ii) even when alignment is sound, the semantics of classes and relationships may vastly differ across domains, which in turn, may create inconsistent alignments; (iii) it does not address the problem in the long-term.

Another possibility is to reuse current ontologies for music metadata, such as the Music Ontology (MO) [36] and the DOREMUS ontology [7]. However, modelling music metadata across different genres and historical periods, to accommodate various use cases over heterogeneous data sources poses a number of challenges. First of all, it requires a perspective that harmonises all requirements from different stakeholders – to design a model that can be tailored to different data sources rather than to a single type of dataset. We categorise the main challenges and requirements for metadata interoperability as follows. Nonetheless, analogous considerations can be drawn for other areas that are of interest to Polifonia, such as musical content, annotations, and instruments.

Domain specificity hampers interoperability

When looking at current ontologies, MO leans towards modelling discographic data with a focus on contemporary music, whereas DOREMUS is inherently rooted in classical music. These ontologies have been demonstrated to model metadata from MusicBrainz and BBC Music [37], and from classical music libraries and radio broadcasts for concerts programming [38], respectively. Their specificity makes them appealing when downstream applications show considerable overlap in terms of requirements and data. Examples include the reuse of MO in the WASABI project [39], to support the semantic annotation of audio music (emotions, lyrics, structures), but also for music recommendation [40] and listening [41]; and the adoption of DOREMUS by *Philharmonie de Paris*, *Bibliothèque Nationale de France*, and *Radio France*.

Nevertheless, when drifting from discographic data and classical music, or attempting to reuse both models, addressing e.g. cultural heritage requirements while fostering interoperability becomes difficult. Indeed, a model reflecting the view and the interpretations ascribable to a musical genre, stakeholder, or dataset type may be difficult to reuse and extend to other domains. For instance, a music artefact may originate from oral transmission or be the result of a creative process that does not necessarily entail a formal composition process. The latter is common in songwriting, but also in folk music whenever a set of tunes (collected from different manuscripts) allows for the identification of a tune family [42]. Similarly, when expressing relationships between musical artefacts (alias derivations), it is important not to impose any modelling bias that may constrain possible interpretations (e.g. an arrangement having proper musical identity vs simply providing a different instrumentation). This is commonly referred to as “dominance of concept” [38], whose definition should be left to users depending on their data and domain expertise.

Rather than attempting to achieve consensus on musical concepts and jargon, accounting for the interoperability calls for an abstraction layer for music metadata (“*zoom-out*”) that can then be specialised, extended, and adapted to address domain-specific requirements (“*zoom-in*”).

Expressivity is needed at different levels

Another requirement for interoperability and reuse across various data sources is providing expressivity at different degrees, i.e. the possibility to conveniently describe music metadata at the right level of detail. For example, one data source may have granular/detailed information that requires high semantic expressivity (a composition process spread over different time, places, and involving more artists); whereas others may have basic (only the name of an artist is known) or even incomplete and uncertain information (a composition tentatively attributed to an artist).

Here, the WikiProject Music⁷ has been successful in providing expressivity to represent music metadata from different sources. As an extreme case of ontological flexibility, the schema underlying Wikidata – an open-ended, multi-domain KG built collaboratively like Wikipedia – is not specified in a previously agreed ontology, and the high expressivity overly adds complexity to the model. This is due to Wikidata’s scope being the most general. Therefore, a tradeoff between expressivity and complexity exists – with a highly expressive model potentially jeopardising its understanding and reuse.

Provenance is central for data integration

Accounting for provenance is a central requirement for both cultural heritage and music industry. This becomes fundamental when integrating Knowledge Graphs from different datasets and stakeholders – as every single bit of data (each triple) should be attributable to a dataset/KG. Furthermore, integrating provenance is also needed within the context of a single dataset, at least for claims and links.

- **Claims-Interpretations.** Cultural heritage applications often require representing debatable statements or claims [43, 44]. These are usually the result of an interpretation process based on factual or documentary evidence (a dataset, a manuscript, etc.), and following a methodology and/or theory. Examples include personal information (e.g. the year/place of birth of a composer), and authorship claims (e.g. a composition being attributed to an artist).
- **Links and identifiers.** These includes links to artists’ official websites, fan pages, discussion forums, music reviews, record shops; as well as identifiers from music databases (e.g. MusicBrainz, Discogs, AllMusic), streaming platforms (e.g. Deezer, Spotify), and authoritative sources (e.g. ISNI, ISWC, ISRC). As most links and identifiers are crowdsourced or automatically inferred by entity linking algorithms, modelling provenance here promotes traceability and accountability of data sources.

Notably, Wikidata addresses both these requirements, as every triple is considered a statement per se, for which so-called *references* can be appended and ranked. References may include information on the source, whether a computational method was used, and a date of retrieval.

1.3 Ontology engineering methodologies

We now address the second challenge behind the design and development of our ontologies in Polifonia. More precisely, here we focus on the ontology engineering methodologies and the complexity of requirements in Polifonia. Various ontology engineering methodologies have been proposed over the years. More recently, due to the inception of the Web and an increasingly connected world, the focus of ontology engineering methodologies has moved towards collaborative ontology engineering [45]. Some of the most prominent ontology engineering methodologies are summarised in this section. A more detailed overview is provided in Deliverable D2.1 [29].

⁷https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:WikiProject_Music

In early works, METHONTOLOGY [46] defined a development process involving the specification, conceptualisation, formalisation, implementation, and maintenance steps. It refers to [47] for the requirements elicitation step, needed for conceptualising the domain, and it does not recommend best practices for the ontology development, besides reusing and integrating existing ontologies. The DILIGENT ontology engineering methodology [48] takes into account collaborative aspects and the involvement of different stakeholders. However, it does not provide any guidelines for the design of the ontology, and is not test-oriented.

More recent work including the NEON ontology engineering methodology [49] and SAMOD (Simplified Agile Methodology for Ontology Development)⁸ [50] are more agile and support iterative ontology development. SAMOD defines a set of principles that should guide the ontology design, such as using self-explanatory names for the ontology entities and taking into consideration existing ontologies and ontology design patterns. However, there are no explicit guidelines nor support for the requirements elicitation and ontology testing steps.

The most relevant to our approach is the *eXtreme Design* methodology [51, 52] which is an agile ontology engineering methodology that focuses on, and provides guidelines for, the reuse of ontology design patterns (ODPs), i.e. small reusable modelling solutions to recurrent modelling problems. It is iterative and incremental, involves different actors and teams, and is strongly test-based.

Nonetheless, despite the experience and the level of expertise in mastering an ontology engineering methodology, bottlenecks, ambiguities, and domain jargon can hamper progress from the requirement collection stage. This especially happens when involving several stakeholders and domain experts. The Polifonia Ontology Network described in this deliverable is based on and extends the eXtreme design methodology which is discussed in further detail in the following sections.

1.4 Main contributions of this deliverable

This deliverable mainly describes the creation and content of the **Polifonia Ontology Network (PON)**, a set of new ontologies formalising the semantics of music representation, metadata, annotation, analysis, mediums of performance (instruments), and historical sources (provenance), enabling the creation of interoperable knowledge graphs from music datasets. To achieve this, we apply and extend eXtreme Design (XD) [51], a well-known ontology design methodology where ontological requirements are gathered from a comprehensive inventory of competency questions (CQs), and modularity is fostered through the reuse of Ontology Design Patterns (ODPs) [53, 54]. We also release the PolifoniaCQ dataset, a collection of 361 competency questions on musical heritage.

Further, we validate PON and provide evidence of its current and planned (re)use by three different types of users: (i) the Polifonia pilots, using them to generate musical culture KGs; (ii) a number of industrial and institutional stakeholders and early adopters, planning to use PON to annotate their in-house datasets; and (iii) a survey run in the Semantic Web and Music Technology communities showing intentions of use. Testing of PON ontologies will be addressed in D2.8 (*Ontology testing and evaluation report; knowledge graph documentation and access interfaces*).

More specifically, the contributions of this deliverable are outlined as follow:

- *Extensions to XD* centred around CQ extraction and enhancement, including both methodological (a CQ-elicitation framework to mirror use cases from domain experts) and technological (a toolkit for assisted design and iterative improvement of CQs through language models) aspects (Section 2.1).
- *PolifoniaCQ*, a new dataset of competency questions driving the design and the evaluation of PON, with associated stories and personas – collected and iteratively enhanced throughout the project (Section 2.1.1).
- The *Polifonia Ontology Network (PON v1.0)* resources, available on GitHub⁹ and including 15 ontology modules, released under the CC-BY 4.0 license. This is complemented by documentation, examples, and software to facilitate the understanding, reuse, and extension of PON resources. (Chapter 2).
- *Evidence of reuse* and impact from music stakeholders, applications and KGs from Polifonia pilots, and interest from various research communities (Section 3.3).

⁸<https://essepuntato.it/samod/>

⁹<https://github.com/polifonia-project/ontology-network>

- Creative use cases of PON resources for harmonic similarity, pattern finding, and assisted music composition.

Compared to previous/other deliverables:

- We focus on the design and the development cycle followed to build, document, and validate the ontology modules in PON in their first stable version since the project inception. This differs from D2.1 [29], where the first draft of the ontology network was presented, in addition to the literature review supporting this contribution.
- We do not cover the experimental results carried out to evaluate the methods for computational music analysis in Section 3.4; here we focus on the methods underpinning the creation of our Knowledge Graphs. More details on our experiments can be found at [55], and will be documented in D3.6 (*Software for classifying music objects according to the extracted patterns and their relation, used as features*).
- The deliverable emphasises the main developments in our ontologies, and their application for the creation of the current KGs by the Polifonia pilots. This differs from D2.3 [56], which focused on progress achieved on ontologies for musical object contexts. We remark that PON has undergone a major refactoring compared to the aforementioned deliverable and it is now in a stable version.

2 The Polifonia Ontology Network: building a semantic backbone for musical heritage

The Polifonia Ontology Network (PON) [57] addresses the aforementioned challenges by integrating heterogeneous requirements related to musical content and contexts into a modular yet unified architecture. It brings interoperability of music metadata and content at different abstraction levels focus on the similarity of the diversity and the complementary nature of its requirements. The design of PON is described in Section 2.1; the ontologies it comprehends – starting from the foundational models providing the highest level of abstraction, are introduced in Section 2.2; and the most advanced modules for the annotation and analysis of musical content are explained in Section 2.3.

2.1 The eXtreme Design methodology in Polifonia

To develop PON, we rely on, and extend, the eXtreme Design [51, 52] (XD) ontology engineering methodology. As mentioned in Section 1.3, we recall that XD fosters the reuse of ontology design patterns (ODPs) [53, 54] and provides support to incrementally address small sets of requirements formalised as competency questions (CQs). This minimises the impact of changes in future releases, which is beneficial to Polifonia (heterogeneous project requirements and participants). Moreover, our ontology designers have relevant experience in using this methodology.

The application of XD iterates over a series of steps, for which we detail their process while highlighting our main extensions. These are illustrated in Figure 2.1 and detailed in the following subsections.

2.1.1 Requirements collection

Ontological requirements are collected from *customers* in the form of *user stories* (e.g. “*Tosca* was performed in Rome on 14 January 2000”), which are then translated as competency questions (CQs) – the natural language counterpart of structured queries that the resulting KG should answer [58]. For instance, the previous story may become “*Where was a musical piece performed?*”.

We borrow techniques from User eXperience design [59] to extend this framework with 3 new sections in the story template: *persona*, *goal*, and *scenario*. The *persona* is a research-based description of a typical user: name, age, occupation, skills and interests. The *goal* is a short textual description of what the persona aims to achieve in the story, complemented by a list of keywords (maximum 5) provided by the customers. The *scenario* describes how the persona’s goals are currently solved, to contextualise the gap with the resource being developed.

In cooperation with the domain experts in Polifonia (music historians, librarians, computational musicologists, music analysts, archivists, data engineers, etc.), 22 personas have been created¹ from this step.

Iterative refinement of CQs. Competency questions were then analysed to identify any inconsistencies that could create obstacles for ontology design. Common inconsistencies were due to vague concepts, for instance, the assertion of two compositions being *connected* without any specific context (in terms of the property) on which the connection can be established (e.g. similar melodies, rhythm). Other CQs were found to be overly complex or nested – entailing more than a single requirement as a result of nested logical operators articulating the question (e.g. “*How is track B connected to C to conclude D?*”). Such CQs needed to be conceptually simplified before being processed further.

To efficiently address these inconsistencies, we developed the *Infer, DEsign, CreAte* (IDEA) framework: analytical tools for CQ-driven ontology design based on language models². IDEA automatically extrapolates and organises

¹<https://github.com/polifonia-project/stories>

²<https://github.com/polifonia-project/idea>

Figure 2.1: Summary of the main Polifonia extensions to the eXtreme Design methodology.

CQs from a source repository, analyses them to find inconsistencies and similarities, and visually projects them to a sentence-level embedding space [60]. The framework has enabled the iterative refinement and improvement of CQs through human-machine collaboration: questions are first extracted and preliminary validated by tagging them (complex, nested, ill-formed, passing), then brought to the attention of the corresponding ontology designer whenever their intervention is needed. To date, 3 cycles of CQ improvement have been completed with IDEA. Instead, the analysis of CQ embeddings through similarity facilitated the identification of overlapping requirements from the pilots (beyond the syntactic level); which in turn enabled and fuelled discussion from various experts and pilots during our ontology design meetings (e.g. 2 CQs may have similar interpretation or semantics for OD, but entail different semantics across pilots).

The PolifoniaCQ dataset. At the end of this process, we obtained 361 CQs, which are systematically collected in the PolifoniaCQ dataset [57] with pointers to their personas and stories. We make this dataset available under CC-BY 4.0³. Future versions of the dataset – providing additional or enhanced requirement in the form of competency questions, can be efficiently published whenever a new iteration of IDEA is completed. This is illustrated in the feedback loop involving XD users and the OD team that illustrated in Figure 2.2.

2.1.2 Ontology network design and development

Clustering CQs as ontology modules. The refined CQs could then be translated in clear, atomic and consistent ontological requirements. Given the wide diversity of CQs – ranging from general events to musicological interpretations of specific passages in compositions, the first step was to achieve a meaningful categorisation into thematic clusters. This step led to the definition of the ontology modules shaping the architecture of PON.

To streamline this process, we analysed the CQ embedding space generated and projected by IDEA. This is done by computing the sentence-level embeddings (a numerical vector of fixed size that is supposed to capture the meaning of a sentence) for each CQ in the PolifoniaCQ dataset. The latter can be considered as a point in a high dimensional space – providing a numerical summary of the question’s meaning [61]. Embeddings are computed via Sentence-

³<https://github.com/polifonia-project/polifoniacq-dataset>

Figure 2.2: Overview of the workflow implementation with the IDEA framework: starting from the stories, the extraction and preliminary validation of competency questions, and their iterative improvement through the interaction between the XD users and the OD team. This is complemented by the suite of analytical methods (embeddings, clustering, search), accelerating the activities of the OD team.

BERT [62] due to its state of the art performance on a number of question-related tasks, including multi-lingual search and paraphrase detection.

An interactive visualisation of the PolifoniaCQ embeddings is available from a live Tensorboard Projector [60] (hosted by Google) which is set up and synchronised via IDEA⁴. The qualitative analysis of the embedding space, in addition to density-based clustering analysis under various parametrisations, have jointly facilitated the identification of common requirements (as nested clusters) and enabled the interactive exploration of the PolifoniaCQ dataset via similarity (c.f. Figure 2.3).

Matching CQs to ODPs. For each module/ontology, an XD iteration starts from selecting a coherent set of CQs. To address those requirements, existing solutions (ODPs) from ontologies or online catalogues of patterns⁵ are considered for reuse, extension, and specialisation. For instance, a CQ such as “Where and when a situation took place?” can be matched to the *TimeIndexedSituation*⁶ ODP, which represents temporal situations.

Here, IDEA supports the identification of “the CQ set” via the multi-lingual search feature. For example, an ontology designer looking for CQs related to places may express a search query as shown below in Listing 2.1.

Listing 2.1: Search results for query “questions related to places” with similarity score.

1	0.377	Where were the places in which musicians played?
2	0.368	Which are all organs near to geographic coordinates x, y?
3	0.341	What are geographically distinct features of organs from a region?
4	0.287	Where is the church/bell tower?
5	0.285	What is the provenance of the event attendees?
6	0.275	Which tunes which share melodic patterns or geographical origin?
7	0.265	What places did a musician visited in her career?
8	0.263	Where is the Bell Tower?
9	0.246	Where was a musical composition performed?
10	0.238	In which buildings was a musical composition performed?

⁴From <https://polifonia-project.github.io/idea/competency-questions/>

⁵See for example ontologydesignpatterns.org

⁶<http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:TimeIndexedSituation>

Figure 2.3: Visualisation of the Polifonia CQ embeddings using a TensorBoard projector instance.

Direct/indirect ontology reuse. Depending on the project’s requirements, reuse of ontologies and ODPs is direct and/or indirect [63]. The former approach directly includes/imports ontologies or part of them (e.g. individual entities, relations) thus introducing a dependency to any possible changes and availability. In indirect reuse, relevant entities and patterns from other ontologies are used as templates (replicated and extended) while being aligned to ensure interoperability. In Polifonia, we follow a hybrid approach: ArCo ontology [6] is directly reused since its development and maintenance involves one of the project’s partners (MiC), while others (such as DOREMUS) are indirectly reused and aligned. Alignment is achieved through equivalent and close match statements for both classes and properties. This is also motivated by the active involvement of our ontology design team in the ArCo project, which facilitate the adopt and the maintenance of this contribution in Polifonia.

Validation and testing. Ontology modules have been developed in close collaboration with domain experts and pilot leaders throughout the whole development cycle. This has allowed the ontology design team to leverage the domain expertise in Polifonia to technically validate our modules at different stages: from the collection and analysis of requirements, to iterations of ontology designs. Validation was facilitated by IDEA, given the possibility to inspect similar, or potentially contrasting, requirements from the CQs. For modelling and fast prototyping, we relied on the Graphical Framework For OWL Ontologies (Graffoo) notation [64] – providing a powerful visual language for coproduction activities. This has also been achieved through data snippets provided by the pilots, which have been modelled by our ontologies and triggered further iterations of improvements.

2.2 Foundational models and their extensions and specialisations

The Polifonia Ontology Network (PON) provides a modular backbone of music ontologies to address both cultural heritage and more general queries in the music domain. As illustrated in Figure 2.4, PON v1.0 comprises 15 ontology modules that are organised thematically (colours, horizontal view) and hierarchically, to highlight their dependencies (vertical view). At the bottom of the architecture lies our Core module (providing general-purpose elements of design, ODPs, and alignments) and the reused ontologies. Four foundational models provide interoperability across

Figure 2.4: Overview of the main modules in the Polifonia Ontology Network, with Polifonia’s pilots as early adopters (grey circles). Foundational models (*Source*, *Instrument*, *Music Meta*, *Music Representation*) provide the backbone of PON, built on top of the *Core* module while leveraging the main ontologies reused directly or indirectly.

PON through their abstract design: *Source*, *Instrument*, *Music Meta*, and *Music Representation*. These are specialised and extended in the upper levels to add functionalities and contextualise specific domains. Notably, the abstract scope of the foundational models is expected to provide a general descriptive level for the corresponding thematic areas (music metadata, instruments, representations, and sources) that does not introduce or enforce any particular bias/specificity ascribable to a genre, style, time period, and interpretation. This is a requirement by design, as it ensures interoperability of the ontology modules at the higher levels in PON. Domain specificity (e.g. genres, styles) and additional requirements (e.g. modelling a new instrument) can be addressed by specialising and extending our foundational modules (as done, for example, in *Tunes* for folk music metadata, and for *Organs* and *Bells* from *Music Instrument*, etc.).

A summary of PON modules is given in Table 2.1, with links to the repositories storing the modules with documentation, diagrams, and examples. Through our foundational models, PON ontologies can be applied to a wide set of music projects, and the modular design simplifies extensibility and maintenance. To facilitate this process, we are also creating additional documentation, tutorials, and examples on a website dedicated to PON, which can be accessed at the following link <https://polifonia-project.github.io/ontology-network/>. After all modules have been presented, we also provide an example describing music metadata and content by leveraging 5 ontologies in PON, in addition to the *Core* module (Section 2.19).

2.2.1 The Music Meta module

This foundational ontology provides a rich and flexible ontology to describe music metadata related to artists, compositions, performances, recordings, broadcasts, and links. *Music Meta* [65] focuses on provenance and interoperability – essential requirements for the integration of music datasets, which is currently hampered by the specificity of existing ontologies. The model is based on the Information-Realisation ODP [66], allowing to reduce complexity of

The Polifonia Ontology Network
10.5281/zenodo.7919970

Module	Prefix	Outline	Repository
Core	core:	Elements of general reuse and ontology design patterns	/core-ontology
Music Meta	mm:	Achieving interoperability of music metadata	/music-meta-ontology
Music Representation	mr:	Foundational model to describe arbitrary musical content	/music-representation-ontology
Music Instrument	mop:	Instruments and their evolution through time and space	/music-instrument-ontology
Source	src:	Musical sources and their context of production	/source-ontology
Tunes	tunes:	A specialisation of Music Meta for folk music	/tunes-ontology
CoMeta	com:	An extension of Music Meta to represent music corpora	/cometa-ontology
Music Projection	mp:	Achieving interoperability of music notation systems	/music-projection-ontology
Organs	organs:	A rich descriptive model of organs and building methods	/organs-ontology
Bells	bell:	Describing bells, bell towers and bell ringers	/bell-ontology
Music Algorithm	mx:	Computational methods for music and their parametrisation	/music-algorithm-ontology
Music Analysis	ma:	Music analysis through reasoning using modal-tonal theories	/music-analysis-ontology
Music Annotation	ann:	A wrapper of ontologies for music annotations (audio, symbolic)	/music-annotation-ontology
PON (full)	pon:	The whole Polifonia Ontology Network (imports all modules).	/ontology-network

Table 2.1: Overview of the modules in the Polifonia Ontology Network. All URIs are also accessible from <https://github.com/polifonia-project/ontology-network>.

FRBR-based models, whose application in the music domain has raised concerns [67]. To enable data integration from existing knowledge bases and datasets, we also align to Music Ontology [5], DOREMUS [21], and Wikidata.

At the core of Music Meta lies the use of the Information-Realisation (IR) ODP [66]. An *information object* is a non-physical social object carrying information that can have one or multiple materialisations (*information realisations*). Each realisation is a particular physical object, or event, realising the the *information object*, or involving the latter as a participant. Both information object and realisation are intended as information entities (IE), i.e. (social) objects created and/or used to communicate, reason, and specify new entities. This allows to distinguish between a piece of information (e.g. the *content* of a composition) from how it is materialised (e.g. as a performance).

On the other hand, both the Music Ontology [36] and DOREMUS [38] are built on top of different flavours of FRBR [68] (FRBRer and FRBRoo, respectively). FRBR is a conceptual model describing bibliographic resources at four levels: *Work*, *Expression*, *Manifestation*, and *Item*. In contrast, the two levels of the IR pattern map to *Expression* and *Item*, since *Work* and *Manifestation* are said to provide non-informative conceptualisations [66]. Moreover, [67] argues that FRBR’s Works – intended as “entities that pre-exist expressions”, cannot represent improvisations or traditional music, as they do not derive from a formal composition process leading to a realisation. FRBR’s Work is often ambiguously intended as an entity retrospectively created for grouping multiple expressions for cataloguing needs. As for the Manifestation level, while its representation is straightforward in the bibliographic domain (e.g. the printed version of a book), its correspondence in the music domain is not fully intuitive, as it may relate to either a recording, a score, a compact disc, or all the above – thereby introducing complexity and ambiguity.

Nevertheless, being aligned to two levels of FRBR, the IR ODP makes our model leaner and flexible, while still achieving interoperability with FRBR-based (music) ontologies. In fact, IE patterns are meant to boost the semantic integration of contents, tools, platforms, resources that are silo-ed or non-interoperable [66].

Main elements of design

From PolifoniaCQ dataset, we identified those related to metadata, and aimed for a model capable to address the requirements in Section 1.2. Music Meta follows a hierarchical design (where each level extends the former to add expressiveness) and is complemented by data transformation rules to conveniently translate one level into another.

To enable data integration from existing knowledge bases and datasets, we align Music Meta to other ontologies: the Music Ontology, DOREMUS, and Wikidata, after having identified common/similar classes and properties.

Figure 2.5: Describing music artists as musicians, music ensembles, and algorithms using the Grafoo notation (yellow boxes are classes, blue/green arrows are object/datatype properties, purple circles are individuals, green polygons are datatypes).

Music artists. To represent music creatives the class `mm:MusicArtist` generalises over musicians (`mm:Musician`), ensembles (`mm:MusicEnsemble`), and computational methods (`mm:MusicAlgorithm`), as illustrated in Figure 2.5. Musicians are seen as a specialisation of persons who can optionally be associated to a medium of performance (e.g. voice, guitar), and be part of a music ensemble (e.g. `MusicGroup`, `Orchestra`, `Choir`). Depending on the data available, the latter can be expressed either through a membership relationship (`core:isMemberOf`), a specialisation of the former, such as `mm:isSingerOf`, or through a `mm:MusicEnsembleMembership` when the period of participation of the musician is available.

All music artists can be associated to (one or more) `mm:MusicGenre(s)`, express influences or collaborations, and share a period of activity. Here, the start date refers to the foundation for music ensembles, whereas the end date is used for discontinued projects for algorithms.

Figure 2.6: Abstracting music inception as an product of a creative process, involving music artists in activities (music writing, instrumentation, etc.), defined in time and space and according to different roles.

Music inception. The focal point of Music Meta is the `mm:MusicEntity` class (Figures 2.6 and 2.7). This class represents an Information Object, which is defined as the sum of all the elements that make up a piece of music. A Music Entity is composed of several components, including lyrics (generalised through `mm:Text` to also account for `mm:Libretto`), the entailed musical content (`mm:AbstractScore`) and its instrumentation (`mm:Instrumentation`).

A `mm:AbstractScore` provides an abstraction to describe the musical properties of an entity, such as the form

Figure 2.7: Describing a music entity and the elements it contains: Text, AbstractScore and Instrumentation.

of a piece (`mm:FormType`), its constituents parts (e.g. `mm:Movement` or `mm:Section`), and its key (`mm:Key`). Datatype properties also describe the tempo of the composition (`mm:tempo`) and its order (`mm:orderNumber`). A `mm:Instrumentation` can instead be formalised in a `mm:Score`, which can be either digital or paper. Through the score, the instrumentation describes one or more `mm:MediumOfPerformance`, each of which has a cardinality (e.g. 3 violins).

It is also possible to describe relationships between different Music Entities, defined by parthood (`mm:hasPart`) and derivation (`mm:isDerivedFrom`). Derivations are used at the user's discretion, based on the dominance of concept [38] (whose criteria attribute proper identity to a musical entity) and can be of different types: revision, transposition, cover, reconstruction, reduction, etc. This makes it possible to describe different types of compositions, rearrangements and modifications of an original piece, as well as influences and more complex types of derivations. Examples of derivations that can be seamlessly reused in Music Meta can be found from the controlled vocabularies of DOREMUS [69]⁷. For example, the production of a cover song (e.g. in a different musical genre) may keep the lyrics and introduce a new composition and instrumentation, hence resulting in a new `mm:MusicEntity`. In addition, Music Entities can be organised in `mm:Collection`, according to a `mm:CollectionConcept` that binds them together.

In sum, the model provides flexibility across periods and genres as the proposed classes allow generalisations to be made about the text, the musical composition and its arrangement. (c.f. Section 1.2). Through the specialisation of classes, depending on the target domain/application, specificity can easily be achieved (c.f. Section 1.2). For example, a tune family can be seen as a `mm:Collection` encompassing several tunes (as music entities) based on specific criteria (e.g. similarity, provenance).

From performance to recording and broadcast. The realisation of a `mm:MusicEntity` is exemplified by `mm:MusicalPerformance`, which can be either live (`mm:LivePerformance`) or in a studio (`mm:StudioPerformance`). As illustrated in Figure 2.8, the place and time interval of a performance are described by `core:Place` and `core:TimeInterval` – involving one or more music artists (optionally, with a specific role). A performance may also create a new `mm:MusicEntity` if, e.g., the execution differs significantly from the original version.

A Music Entity can also be recorded by means of a `mm:RecordingProcess`, which is a subclass of a `mm:CreativeProcess`. This makes it possible to describe information about both the production (e.g., producers) and the technical aspects of it (e.g., sound engineer, equipment used). The recording process produces a `mm:Recording`, which is contained in a `mm:Release`.

⁷See also: <https://data.doremus.org/vocabularies/>

Figure 2.8: Describing performance, recording, broadcasting, publication, and licensing.

Information about the broadcasting of a recording is modelled through the `mm:BroadcastingSituation` class (an instance of the Situation ODP [70]), which describes when and where the song was broadcast, and by which broadcaster (`mm:Broadcaster`).

Publishing and licensing information. The `mm:PublicationSituation` class describes information about the publication of a release, which is common to the publication of a `mm:Score` (c.f. Figure 2.8). For both a release and a score, it describes when and where they were published, and by a `mm:Publisher`.

Licence information is described by the `mm:License` class, which applies to records, releases and scores.

Conversion rules and code support

To facilitate the reuse of Music Meta and its data conversion into OWL/RDF Knowledge Graphs, we developed `PyMusicMeta` – a library to map arbitrary music metadata into RDF triples. This enables a practical and scalable workflows for data lifting to create Music KGs without expert knowledge of our ontological model. The library is developed in Python as an extension of RDF-Lib [71].

With each triple, `PyMusicMeta` adds alignments to the supported schema whenever possible. For example, the pseudo triple `<DavidBowieURI, rdf:type, mm:Musician>` in Music Meta will be complemented with `<DavidBowieURI, rdf:type, http://purl.org/ontology/mo/MusicArtist>` for Music Ontology, `<DavidBowieURI, rdf:type, http://erlangen-crm.org/E21_Person>` for DOREMUS (via the Erlangen Conceptual Reference Model [72]) and `<DavidBowieURI, rdf:type, https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q639669>` for Wikidata; to achieve interoperability of the Music KG.

2.2.1.1 The Tunes module

This ontology extends and specialises Music Meta for folk music (Figure 2.9). The main novelty consists in grouping and describing tunes into “tune families” depending on their melodic similarity (an association requiring rich provenance description of the musicological analysis on the source); which also extends to lyrics families. In particular, each `tunes:Tune` is seen as a specialisation of a `mm:MusicEntity` that may belong to a `tunes:TuneFamily`, which in turn specialises `core:Collection` (please, note that the term `Collection` is seen from an ontology engineering perspective, as this reuses the `Collection` ontology design pattern in Music Meta).

As can be seen from the diagram/example below, the membership of a `tunes:Tune` to `tunes:TuneFamily` is described by `core:CollectionMembership`, which provides additional information on the actual strength of such membership. The latter is captured by `core:CollectionMembership`, which is specialised by two entities here: `tunes:WeakFamilyMembership` and `tunes:NeutralFamilyMembership`.

Another extension that is peculiar to folk music, is the possibility to group tunes’ `mm:Lyrics` into a `tunes:LyricsFamily`. This is analogous to `tunes:TuneFamily` as described above. The same criteria

Figure 2.10: Overview of the main classes and properties of CoMeta, for the semantic description of datasets.

- License/Copyright: to represent the licensing and copyright information associated with the dataset. Notably, this can be achieved at different levels (a subset of the collection may follow different licensing scheme) and content (e.g. annotation and musical content are distributed according to different licenses).
- References: to provide links to official websites and academic manuscripts describing the dataset and its collection process, facilitating proper citation and reference.

Overall, by incorporating and supporting these requirements, the ontology provides a structured representation of music datasets, their metadata, annotations, and interconnections. Besides the Polifonia project, the use of the CoMeta ontology when releasing music datasets can potentially enable researchers and practitioners to explore, analyse, and utilise the datasets more effectively, promote interoperability (especially when overlapping content is found), and facilitate the automatic discovery and extraction of knowledge from music-related data.

2.2.2 The Music Representation module

This module provides a comprehensive schema to describe the analysis of musical objects (a score, an audio track, etc.) interpreted according to a music theory. Fragments of a musical object (elements of a music object whose temporal location is uniquely identifiable) are described by annotations provided by an agent (e.g. expert annotator, algorithm). An annotation is either the subjective result of an analysis (e.g. a chord played in a specific section) or objective in nature (e.g. a note in a digital score). Each annotation describes some music content (e.g. notes, chords, etc.), which we refer to as a *musical projection* [73]. Annotations are formalised via our Music Annotation Pattern [74], whereas the definition of music projections is delegated to the Music Projection module. The generality of the module and its abstraction over the represented content enables the interoperability of different music annotation schema. The module is aligned to MusicOWL [19], Music Notation Ontology [75], Music Note Ontology [76], and our JAMS ontology (c.f. Section 2.3).

Figure 2.11: Music representation schema.

Module design

The Music Representation module allows the description of different data sources, described by the Music Meta module (c.f. 2.2.1), through the use of the `mr:MusicContent` class (Figure 2.11). Three main elements jointly contribute to the description of a `mr:MusicContent`: `mr:Analysis`, `mr:Annotation` and `mr:Fragment`. A `mr:Fragment` describes a uniquely identifiable instant on a music entity. Such instant is temporally identified by means of the `core:MusicTimeInterval` class, which allows different temporal locations (e.g. beats, seconds, characters, centimetres in the picture of a score, etc.) to straightforwardly coexist. A `mr:Fragment` is connected directly to a `mr:MusicContent` instance (`mr:hasFragment` property), to state the membership of a fragment in the respective musical entity, or it is connected to a `mr:Annotation` instance (`mr:describesFragment` property), when the identified element is the result of an analysis by some agent. The `mr:Annotation` class represents the annotating act of an agent on some musical content. When an annotation describes objectively identifiable information it is directly connected to a `mr:MusicContent` through the `mr:hasAnnotation` property. If the annotation is the result of a subjective analytical process it is connected to the `mr:Analysis` class through the same `mr:hasAnnotation` property. The `mr:Analysis` class describes the analytical process where an agent explicitly labels a music content in the context of a specific music theory. The class `mr:AnalyticalReference` is used to describe the musical theory used through the use of the `core:isExplanationBasedOn` property. An analysis is indeed the explanation of the annotations performed and it changes depending on the theoretical frame in use. Both `mr:Analysis` and `mr:AnalyticalReference` allows the definition of metadata information, such as agents involved and their roles.

The concept identified by the annotator through an annotation is modelled through the use of the `mr:Observation` class. A `mr:Annotation`, which can be defined by referencing other annotations as well, might have multiple different observations. Multiple observation can refer to the same annotation, e.g. when describing the chord in a segment the annotator is implicitly observing the presence of a chord and its rhythmic duration, which are two distinct conceptual elements. The identified concepts are described by means of a `mr:MusicProjection` through the `mr:hasSubject` property. Additional metadata information, such as the agent performing an annotation or the type of annotation can be described (see Figure 2.11).

In Figure 2.12 an example of the use of the representation module is described. Two distinct music entities are represented: a recording version, which has been described through the use of textual annotation (right), and a

Figure 2.12: Music representation example on the first two chords of “Highway Star” by “Deep Purple”.

recording of a live performance, which has been described through the use of JAMS [77] annotations (left). Despite being the result of two distinct analytical processes, both annotations refer to the same exact musical fragment which are located in different places on the two entities. This is identified through the use of the `skos:exactMatch` predicated, provided by the SKOS schema [78].

2.2.3 The Music Projection module

This module formalises musical entities that can be the subject of an annotation. This ranges from traditional musical notation (e.g. notes, chords) to informal annotations (e.g. mood, danceability). We refer to these musical entities as music projections [73] that are eventually identified by an analytical process. When an annotation is performed on a musical entity, it does not directly add new information to the entity itself but rather adds new information in the sense that the readers will gain knowledge on the entity they did not have before. Nothing new is added that was not already in the piece. Through the annotation process, an agent is able to direct the attention of the reader to specific projections of the musical content, highlighting aspects that were previously implicit [73].

As an exhaustive enumeration of the possible projections is not possible, we expect this module to grow into further subdivisions (sub-modules).

The current set of identified projections (Figure 2.13) is a set of concepts which are considered to be stable across different theories and time periods. A music projection can be seen as the *interpretation* of a musical concept defined by some music theories. For this reason, it is impossible to uniquely model a musical concept (e.g. a chord) such that it satisfies theories spanning different music epochs and genres. Such definition is performed by the Music Analysis Module (c.f. Section 2.3.2), which extends the basic projections of Figure 2.13 in the context of relevant musicological theories.

Currently, the module is aligned with MusicOWL [19], Music Notation Ontology [75], Music Note Ontology [76], Music Theory Ontology [15], Chord Ontology [16], and Roman Chord Ontology⁸.

2.2.4 The Instrument Module

Instrument describes musical instruments as mediums of performance and their technical properties. Given that numerous taxonomies of instruments into *groups* and *families* exist (e.g. Hornbostel-Sachs, MIMO, MusicBrainz) and finding common categorisations is an open problem [12], our module provides an abstraction capable to express

⁸<https://github.com/polifonia-project/roman-chord-ontology>

Figure 2.13: Music Projection schema.

arbitrary classifications. This is achieved by leveraging the Information-Realisation and the Collection ODPs. Overall, the module allows to: (i) refer to instruments as entities (an instrumentation of a piece for “piano” and “viola”) as well as conceptually (e.g. a viola has 4 strings); (ii) support the integration with different taxonomies and vocabularies [69]; (iii) describe the evolution of instruments in time and space (e.g. a viola as a cultural heritage object being relocated). This provides a foundational level where contributors can “plug” their instrument-specific ontologies [79].

The Instrument module reuses the ArCo ontology network. Figure 2.14 depicts the main entities of the module: a `mi:Instrument` can have multiple `mi:InstrumentParts`, and is related to its inventor (`mi:wasInventedBy`), and the time interval when it was invented (`mi:wasInventedAtTime`). Then, after being invented, an instrument can have multiple `mi:InstrumentRealisations`, linked to the instrument itself with the property `core:realises`. The instrument realisation is related to the place and time where/when it was built, the builder, its locations over time, and its actual name.

2.2.4.1 The Bells module

The Bells Ontology extends `Instrument` to describe bells by means of measurable, intrinsic aspects such as weight, materials, conservation status. The main entities contextualising bells are: (i) the author(s), such as the foundry who built the bell; (ii) the agencies that played some role e.g. the agency that took care of cataloguing the bell; (iii) the place(s) where it has been located; (iv) the tower(s) where the bell has been included; (v) the tools that the set of bells is played with; (vi) documents related to the bells, e.g. bibliographies, protective measures.

The Bells ontology module reuses and extends the ArCo ontology network [6, 80].

As in Figure 2.15, a `bell:Bell` can be part of a `bell:SetOfBells`. Such set of bells is linked to an `a-cd:AuthorshipAttribution`, as the interpretation process of attributing an object to an author, having a specific `roapit:Role`. The set of bells could have multiple locations over time, such as the location where it was melted, or its current location e.g. in a bell tower of a church, and this is modelled through the `a-loc:TimeIndexedTypedLocation` class. A set of bells can also be linked to different `a-cd:Dating` situations, such as when it was melted, or when it was moved to another place for restoration. Properties for relating the set of bells with relevant documents in its lifecycle are `a-cd:hasObservationSurvey`, `a-cd:hasProtectiveMeasure`, and `a-cd:hasDocumentation`. Finally, examples of agent that the set of bells could be linked to are expressed by the properties `arco:hasCataloguingAgency` and `arco:hasHeritageProtectionAgency`.

Figure 2.14: Instrument schema.

2.2.4.2 The Organs module

It extends *Instrument* to describe organs as (i) a musical instrument consisting of parts; and (ii) as a focal point of *projects* detailing its changes throughout time. To address the former, we used the Parthood pattern from the DOLCE ontology⁹. The entities of the ODP, *Whole* and *Part* make possible the specification of the whole instrument and its parts. In the ontology, the *Whole* entity refers to the organ instrument, and the *Part* entity refers to the parts of the organ that are *Console*, *WindSystem*, *Case*, *Division*, and *Action*. Examples of CQs addressed by the ontology are: (i) Who built and/or renovated an organ?; (ii) What was the disposition of the organ at a specific point in time?; (iii) Why is an organ moved to another location?. We remark that the design of the Organs ontology was already detailed in D2.3 [56]; and its integration/contextualisation within PON has now been accomplished.

2.2.5 The Source module

The Source module represents various sources of music-related information. These include manuscripts, textbooks, articles, interviews, reviews, comments, memoirs, etc. of different scope and format (physical, digital). The module aims to provide general support to describe information related to the *creator* and *type* of the source, the *time* and *place* when/where it was created, the *context of production* and *usage*, and the *subject* and *goals*. Although this conceptualisation leans towards bibliographical sources, the module provides expressivity to indicate multimedia documents (e.g. images of scores, audio recording, video). For example, a video recording of a performance can be considered as a musical source – providing documentary evidence of a composition e.g. during an event.

As in Figure 2.16, for some concepts examples of named entities are provided: examples of contexts of production for source are an *src:ArtistCommission* or an *src:Event*, the role of an agent involved in the creation of

⁹<http://www.ontologydesignpatterns.org/ont/dul/DUL.owl>

Figure 2.15: Bells schema.

a source can be `src:Editor`, `src:Translator`, etc. A source can have e.g. `src:Correspondence` or `src:Journal` as its type. The context of usage of a source may be `src:Propaganda`, `Teaching`, and so forth.

2.2.5.1 The Meetups module

The Meetups Ontology describes encounters between people in the musical world in Europe from c. 1800 to c. 1945. Historical meetups, which are the main subject of this module, are described by means of four main components: the people involved in the meetup, for instance, the person that is the subject of interest and the people interacting in the event, the place where the encounter took place (e.g., city, country, venue), the type of event, the reason (e.g., music making, personal life, business, among others) and the date when it took place.

2.2.5.2 The MusicBO module

As described in Deliverable 2.3 [81], the module is developed by following a *KG-to-ontology* process [82]. Ontological axioms, grouped into *patterns*, are empirically generated from the MusicBO knowledge graph – which is built from a textual corpus on music performances and encounters between music-related agents in Bologna since the 17th century. Such patterns include information about the probability of axioms to *happen* (as they are derived from the data). For instance, the probability of instances of the pattern *compose* situation (the process of creating art) to have `NaturalPerson` as range of the `artist` property, is higher than the probability of having an `Organisation` as a composer. In sum, the content of the ontology module is highly dependent on the KG, and the most populated and described entities are: persons, places, organisations, works of art, theatres, and books.

Figure 2.16: Source schema.

2.3 Modules for analysis and annotation of music

2.3.1 The Music Algorithm module

This ontology module formalises algorithms that can operate on music metadata (using the Meta module, c.f. 2.2.1), and musical content (via the representation module, c.f. 2.2.2). The module commitments are similar to those defined by Diamantini et al. in [83]. Indeed, an algorithm is characterised by three main components: a *formalisation*, which can be theoretical (e.g. pseudocode) or executable (e.g. using a programming language); a *parametrisation* (e.g. input data); and the kind of *task* it solves (Figure 2.17). The latter defines a set of entities that are processed alongside the input and output data requirements and the final goal achieved. The module allows theoretical and quantitative performances to be represented in the context of the algorithm’s parametrisation. Through an abstract and general definition, the formalisation of the module can be seen as a general pattern, capable of representing any algorithm regardless of the domain of application. In the context of music, the output of the algorithm is considered an analysis, which is then represented via the `mr:Analysis` class of the Music Representation module (c.f. 2.2.2).

2.3.2 The Music Analysis module

It allows for the analysis of musical pieces using historical and present-day established musical theories: the *modal* and *tonal* theories. Through the use of this framework, different subjective analyses can be unified – overcoming the limitations imposed by a “global” theoretical perspective. Different theoretical viewpoints can be used for the interpretation of the same piece. Currently, two historical theories are implemented: Zarlino (1558) and Praetorius (1619) [84, 85]. Through the use of formal reasoning and a comprehensive axiomatisation, the ontology is able to automatically infer the theoretical interpretations of a musical piece and its evolution in time and space. Notably,

Figure 2.17: Music Algorithm schema: a flexible ontology design pattern to describe computational procedures.

we also harmonise different chord representations (Chord Ontology, the Roman Chord Ontology and the Tonality Ontology) formalising the Unified Model of Chords in Western Harmony [86].

2.3.3 The Music Annotation module

The Music Annotation Module is a pivotal component of PON, designed to cater to diverse musicological and information retrieval use cases. By offering a variety of music annotation models, this module aims to enhance the support for various descriptive systems, fostering increased interoperability and enabling seamless conversion between different music annotation formats.

The Music Annotation Module has been enhanced to include the integration of the JAMS Ontology¹⁰ [87]. This ontology serves as a descriptive framework tailored for capturing the JAMS schema [77], encompassing annotations on musical objects such as recordings or scores.

Figure 2.18 represents the schema of the JAMS Ontology. A core class of the JAMS Ontology is the

¹⁰<https://github.com/polifonia-project/jams-ontology>

Figure 2.18: JAMS Ontology schema.

`jams:JAMSAnnotation`. It captures annotations from a file encoded with the JAMS format on a musical object, which can be either a recording or a score. Annotations are related to their musical object through the property `jams:hasJAMSAnnotation`. These annotations include information about the annotator (`jams:Annotator`), time validity (`jams:hasMusicTimeInterval`), and annotation type (`jams:AnnotationType`), such as chords, keys, and more.

The time validity indicates the time frame within the musical object to which the annotation refers. For instance, an annotation about a certain *key* refers to a specific segment of the target musical object. Annotators can be of different types (e.g. expert annotator, software program) and are defined by the class `jams:AnnotatorType`. Each `jams:JAMSAnnotation` consists of observations (`jams:JAMSObservation`), which refer to atomic elements of an annotation. Observations consist of a value (represented by the Music Projection Module, `mp:MusicProjection`), defined at a specific time interval.

Musical time intervals are represented as `core:MusicTimeInterval`, which can be expressed in various ways based on the type of musical object. These intervals are defined by musical time indexes (`core:MusicTimeIndex`), each with start and end components substantiated by a value (`core:hasValue`) and a value type (`core:MusicTimeValueType`). Additionally, musical time intervals have durations expressed through a value and value type (`core:MusicTimeDuration`).

Looking ahead, the Music Annotation Module is poised for further expansion to facilitate interoperability with an array of music annotations across diverse types. This future development aims to provide seamless integration and conversion capabilities for various music annotation formats, enabling researchers, practitioners, and scholars to engage with a broader spectrum of musicological insights.

2.4 Planned extensions and ontologies to be integrated in PON

This section provides an overview of the planned extensions and the ongoing efforts to integrate the resources that have been produced in Polifonia via PON. Such data resources have been produced prior to the development of PON v1.0 and intersect work carried out in various pilots and other work packages. We remark that most contributions mentioned in this section use ad-hoc ontologies and systems that are needed by stakeholders involved in each of this project. Nonetheless, the common denominator enabling the interoperability of these resources is PON, whose alignment makes it possible to reuse them in a distributed manner. As a general strategy, this is being achieved by first identifying classes and properties that can be mapped to PON via alignment; and then adding triples that directly re-use PON ontologies to achieve full compliance. In the following subsections, we provide more detail on the specific integration plans that are being carried out with our pilots.

2.4.1 Metadata ontology from DIRECTUS and annotation ontology

One of the outcomes of the TONALITIES pilot is the DIRECTUS system for organising metadata related to digital scores and their artists. More precisely, DIRECTUS is an open data platform for structuring SQL databases and for efficiently turning them into an API no-code app. The system is available at this link <https://directus.io>.

The ontology that is currently used to semantically describe data in DIRECTUS is illustrated in Figure 2.20 and is based on the LRMoo model. The reuse of this model is a specific requirement for the TONALITIES pilot, as it is warmly suggested by the French National Centre for the Scientific Research (CNRS) for its whole national network of laboratories in human sciences. The same LRMoo model is also applied to the ontology for the analytical annotations made directly on the Collaborative Annotation Interface for Music Analysis, as it is shown in Figure 2.21.

Similarly to the involvement of NISV and the CONCERT KG, CRNS has also provided expertise and feedback to drive the development of music ontologies in WP2. This has allowed to integrate DIRECTUS' ontological requirements within PON and validate the intermediate drafts throughout the design of Music Meta. As this ontology comprehensively addresses the former requirements, ongoing work is being carried out to create alignments between Music Meta and the DIRECTUS model.

2.4.2 Modelling concerts and broadcasts from NISV collections

In the scope of the INTERLINK pilot, NISV has released the CONCERT KG¹¹, a knowledge graph of concert recordings (intended for) broadcast by the Dutch public TV and radio broadcaster. The collection includes information about titles, broadcast date, musical genres, locations and artists related to the concerts. This resource currently uses classes and properties from Schema.org¹². The choice for Schema.org was motivated by the need for a widely supported and easily accessible schema, that supports a wide range of users in searching the collection using the key elements of title, time, person and place.

In the meantime, NISV has provided domain expertise throughout the development of Music Meta, which now provides reasonable expressivity to model performances and broadcasts at the level of detail required for this particular resource. Ongoing efforts are aimed at achieving an alignment with PON that supports querying the key elements of the concert collection. These will be focused on the Core module - namely title, person, time and role information - and the Music Meta module - namely genre, medium, publisher, recording location and broadcaster information.

The relatively flat structure of the NISV data, which combines information on composition, performance, recording and broadcast in the same archive item, means that the richer class structure of PON cannot be fully supported. Alignment will therefore occur at a property level, with the exception of Agents (Person/Organisation) and Places, which are modelled with the same granularity. NISV has worked on Wikidata alignments for musical instruments, to be published in the next release, which could potentially be mapped to the taxonomies in the Instrument module.

¹¹<https://labs.beeldengeluid.nl/blogs/moz-dataset-blog>

¹²<https://schema.org/>

Figure 2.20: Schematic overview of the schema behind the DIRECTUS system from the TONALITIES pilot.

Figure 2.21: Overview of the Collaborative Annotation Interface for Music Analysis from TONALITIES.

2.4.3 Modelling digital music libraries

A part of the work specifically addressed the modelling of digital libraries of scores (DSL), taking as examples either some well-known and widely used digital score libraries such as IMSLP (<http://imslp.org>) or MuseScore (<https://musescore.com>), large legacy institutions such as the Gallica database released by the BnF (<https://gallica.bnf.fr/>) or small, specialised collections published by research institutes, such as the NEUMA¹³ digital library, jointly maintained by two partners of the project: Cnam and IRéMus. The analysis of these DSL, interviews with some of their initial designers and maintainers, and a general set of requirements inferred by inspecting their current functionalities and ongoing projects, led us to the design of a first ontology, called ScoreLib¹⁴, released during the initial phase of the Polifonia project. ScoreLib synthesizes many features common to the aforementioned DSL: references to music scores in various formats, hierarchical organisation of both collections and music entities, notions of *abstract* scores along with their realizations (as concrete objects such as MusicXML files, scans of various score editions, or audio/video recordings), annotations of content, interlinking, and explicit (e.g., authorship) and implicit (e.g., music key) metadata.

¹³<http://neuma.huma-num.fr>

¹⁴<https://github.com/polifonia-project/scorelib-ontology>

As part of the integration efforts in the development of PON, CNAM has joined efforts in WP2, and participated to numerous meetings with ontology experts to leverage ScoreLib, by both abstracting several concepts (e.g., "Opus" in ScoreLib abstracted to the `MusicEntity` concept in PON/Music Meta) and reusing existing ontologies. The rich annotation module designed for ScoreLine has been carefully refactored to preserve compatibility with some existing modules, yet enabling its interoperability with different approaches for the annotation of musical content (JAMS and DIRECTUS' model). ScoreLib has been used to showcase the publication of an existing DSL (namely, Neuma) as linked data, accessible through the Neuma API (<http://neuma.huma-num.fr/home/services>), which can easily be adapted to supply data compliant with the Music Meta module.

2.4.4 Alignment of the Polifonia Lexicon

In collaboration with WP4, we are in the process of aligning the Polifonia Lexicon to the Polifonia Ontology Network. As described in Deliverable 4.1 [88], the Polifonia Lexicon is a plurilingual resource focused on the music domain, created by combining techniques for the automatic extraction from pre-existing lexicographic databases, such as WordNet [89] and BabelNet [90], and a manual improvement through the integration of linguistic data validated by music experts. We pursue the effort of aligning the Polifonia Lexicon to the Polifonia Ontology Network by pivoting on the musicological categories defined with the help of musicologists (such as "performance", "medium of performance", "genre", "performance technique", etc.). On the one hand, these musicological categories will be aligned manually to the Polifonia Ontology Network's classes. On the other hand, the musicological categories' will be associated to each of the Polifonia Lexicon's lemmata by checking if their corresponding BabelNet ID is present in the chain of hypernyms of each of the Polifonia Lexicon's lemmata. As soon as we associate the Polifonia Lexicon's lemmata to the musicological categories, and as soon as the musicological categories are aligned to the Polifonia Ontology Network's classes, we will be able to perform a first automatic alignment of the Polifonia Lexicon lemmata to the Polifonia Ontology Network. The automatic alignment will then be validated by human experts, in particular internship with Knowledge Engineering students or Linguistic students with a Knowledge Engineering background.

3 Adoption, applications, and expected impact

We provide evidence of PON use by Polifonia pilots (Interlink, Tonalities, Meetups, Bells, and MusicBO), which have contributed 6 musical heritage KGs (Section 3.1); and given the scope of this deliverable, here we focus more on KGs related to music objects and patterns. An overview of how PON is being used in Polifonia pilots is reported in Table 3.1 for each module. Potential interest of reuse and opportunities for the Semantic Web and Music Technology communities are collected from an online survey (Section 3.3). In addition, we also report early adopters and ongoing synergies from the Polifonia Stakeholder Network for PON validation and annotation of cultural and industrial datasets (Section 3.2). Finally, we show how PON resources can enable novel workflows and methodologies for computational creativity (Section 3.4).

PON module	Pilots (in use)	Pilots (planned use)
Core	all	all
Music Meta	INTERLINK, TUNES	all
Music Representation	INTERLINK, TONALITIES	FACETS, TUNES
Music Instrument	BELLS, ORGANS	INTERLINK
Source	TUNES	MEETUPS, CHILD
Tunes	TUNES	-
CoMeta	INTERLINK	TUNES, FACETS
Music Projection	INTERLINK	TUNES, FACETS
Organs	ORGANS	-
Bells	BELLS	-
Music Algorithm	TUNES	INTERLINK
Music Analysis	TONALITIES	-
Music Annotation	INTERLINK, TUNES	TONALITIES, FACETS
MusicBo	MUSICBO	

Table 3.1: Current and planned reuse of PON module across Polifonia pilots.

3.1 Current use by Polifonia pilots

3.1.1 Interlink: linking music datasets and musical content via similarity

To date, the Interlink pilot has released ChoCo and Harmory KGs. ChoCo [87] provides 20K+ harmonic annotations of scores and tracks, that were integrated from 18 chord datasets¹. The construction of ChoCo and the integration workflow is reported in Deliverable D2.4 [91], whereas its evaluation is covered in Deliverable D1.5 [92]. The KG uses the JAMS ontology in `Music Annotation`, and the Roman ontology from the `Music Projection` module. Compared to the previous deliverables, ChoCo is also compliant with the `Music Meta` foundational model.

Harmory [55] is a KG of interconnected harmonic patterns derived from the audio subsets ChoCo², and aimed at human-machine creativity (pattern discovery, chord generation, harmonic similarity). The KG is also designed from PON, and comes with software supporting the extraction of harmonic patterns and their comparison via similarity. In particular, Harmory leverages a cognitive model of Western tonal harmony to project chord progressions into a

¹<https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/choco/sparql>

²<https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/harmory/sparql>

Figure 3.1: Overview of the main steps for the creation of Harmony, from the encoding of chord progressions in the Tonal Pitch Space (TPS) and their segmentation from the harmonic self-similarity matrix (SSM), to the emergence of harmonic patterns through similarity and the creation of the KG.

musically meaningful space, and signal processing methods to segment the resulting sequences into meaningful harmonic structures. The latter are then compared with each other, across all progressions and via harmonic similarity, to reveal common/recurring harmonic patterns. The KG is then created to semantically establish relationships between patterns, based on: (i) *temporal links*, connecting two patterns if they are observed consecutively in the same progression; and (ii) *similarity links* among highly-similar patterns. Trivially, identical patterns do not need connections, as they are mapped to the same entity.

The main steps for the creation of Harmony are illustrated in Figure 3.1, and encompass four stages: (i) projection of harmonic sequences in the Tonal Pitch Space; (ii) novelty-based segmentation of harmonic sequences; (iii) pattern identification through similarity-based linking of harmonic segments; and (iii) KG creation.

From ChoCo to Harmory: encoding harmonic sequences

The workflow is defined from the harmonic analysis of a piece in ChoCo, which contains a sequence of *chords* in Harte notation [93], their *onsets*, and the associated local *keys*. Formally, let $c = \{c_1, \dots, c_N\}$ denote a chord sequence of length N , where each chord figure c_i is drawn from the Harte chordal set \mathcal{H} . Similarly, $k = \{k_1, \dots, k_N\}$ denotes the corresponding local keys of c , s.t. each k_i is a tonic-mode tuple defined from $\mathbb{T} \times \mathbb{M}$, where $\mathbb{T} = \{Ab, A, A\#, Bb, \dots, G\#\}$ is the set of all possible tonic notes, and $\mathbb{M} = \{\text{major, dorian}, \dots, \text{locrian}\}$ is the set of all possible modes in Western tonal music.

For simplicity, chords are expected to be temporally aligned with their onsets, meaning that c_i ends when c_{i+1} starts, $\forall i \in N - 1$. Hence, *onsets* are defined as a $(N + 1)$ -th dimensional vector $\mathbf{t} \in \mathbb{R}^{N+1}$ to compensate for the end time of the last chord (t_{N+1} is the end of c_N). Onsets are given in seconds for harmonic analyses on audio music; or as global beats for symbolic music. For example, $c = [G, B:\text{min}, E:\text{min}7, \dots]$, $k = [(G, \text{major}), (G, \text{major}), (G, \text{major}), \dots]$, and $\mathbf{t} = [1, 3, 5, \dots]$ are the first three occurrences of such vectors for a “A Day in the Life” by The Beatles.

Given a harmonic analysis $\mathbf{H} = \{c, k, \mathbf{t}\}$, the first step is to encode c and k as a numerical stream, so as to allow the processing of similarity/distance operations. This is necessary because chords (c) and tonalities (k) are complex elements to process, and come in symbolic format. More specifically, a chord label is a convention for describing intervals built on a root note. For example, the label of a C major seventh chord ($C:\text{maj}7$) represents the intervals of a major quadriad with a minor seventh built on the note C , which is equivalent to the note set $\{C, E, G, Bb\}$. Also, the harmonic function of a chord is contextual to the global (and local) key [94]. We aim for an encoding of harmony that is well established, perceptually and musicologically plausible, and explainable by design. Hence, we rely on the Tonal Pitch Space [95] – a cognitive model of tonality used in music psychology and computational musicology.

Harmonic sequences in the tonal pitch space

The *Tonal Pitch Space* (TPS) model [95] provides a scoring mechanism that predicts the proximity between musical chords. It is based on the Generative Theory of Tonal Music [96] and designed to make explicit music theoretical and cognitive intuitions about tonal organisation. The model works by comparing any possible chord to an arbitrary key, by means of the *basic space*. The basic space includes five different levels, ordered from the most to the least stable: (i) the *Root level*; (ii) the *Fifths level*; (iii) the *Triadic level*; (iv) the *Diatonic level*; and (v) the *Chromatic level*.

Each level holds one or more notes, indexed from 0 (*C*) to 11 (*B*). The *Root level* holds the root of a chord (0 for C-major), while the *Fifths level* adds the fifth (0, 7 for C-major). The *Triadic level* has all the notes in the chord (0, 4, 7 for C major). The *Diatonic level* depends on the chord's key as it holds all the notes of the diatonic scale of the key (0, 2, 4, 5, 7, 9, 11 for the C major key). Finally, the *Chromatic level* holds the chromatic scale (0-11).

The distance between two chords c_i, c_j in keys k_i, k_j is calculated using the *basic spaces* of the chords. The basic space is set to match the key of the pieces (level *iv*), and their levels (*i-iii*) are adapted to match the chords to be compared. The Chord distance rule is applied to calculate the distance. The Chord distance rule is defined as $d(x, y) = j + k$, where $d(x, y)$ is the distance between chord x and chord y ; j is the minimum number of Circle-of-Fifths rule applications to shift x into y , and k is the number of non-common pitch classes divided by 2 in the levels (*i-iv*) of the basic spaces of x and y . The Circle-of-Fifths rule consists in moving the levels (*i-iii*) four steps to the right or left on level *iv*.

For each comparison between two chords, the TPS returns a value in $[0, 13]$. TPS has been demonstrated to be sound both musicologically and perceptually [97, 98], and in this work, it is used to compare chord-key pairs.

Novelty-based harmonic segmentation

The projection of chord-key pairs (c_i, k_i) in the TPS is a fundamental requirement to perform harmonic segmentation. First, the given harmonic annotation \mathbf{H} is used to sample a signal \mathbf{X} of length $d = t_{N+1} \cdot f_s$, where harmonic observation (c_i, k_i) is consecutively repeated $t_i \cdot f_s$ times (its duration), according to a sampling rate f_s . Each element $x_i \in \mathbf{X}$ now encodes an input for the TPS model, containing the harmonic content at the i -th sample.

The resulting signal allows for the computation of two harmonic descriptors, i.e., the *Harmonic Profile* (or TPS time series), and the *Harmonic self-similarity matrix* (SSM) – the entry point for segmentation. The former is defined as a vector $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ s.t. $q_i = \text{tps}(x_i, k_1)$, holding the TPS distance between each harmonic observation x_i and the global key k_1 of the piece (assumed as the first key occurrence). Similarly, the Harmonic SSM is a matrix $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ s.t.

$$\mathbf{S}(n, m) = 1 - \frac{\text{tps}(x_n, x_m)}{13}, \quad (3.1)$$

where $x_i \in \mathbf{X}$ is a column vector; $n, m \in [0 : d - 1]$; 13 is a normalisation factor (the maximum TPS value); and the subtraction from 1 is used to obtain a similarity score from a distance measure.

Self-similarity matrices have been extensively used for structure analysis, due to their ability to reveal nested structural elements [99, 100] As can be seen from Figure 3.2, block-like structures are observed when the underlying sequence shows homogeneous features over the duration of the corresponding segment. Often, such a homogeneous segment is followed by another homogeneous segment that stands in contrast to the previous one.

To identify the boundary between two homogeneous but contrasting segments (2D corner points), we slide a checkerboard kernel \mathbf{K} along the main diagonal of the SSM and sum up the element-wise product of \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{S} . A checkerboard kernel can be simply defined as a box kernel $\mathbf{K}_B \in \mathbb{Z}^{M \times M}$ where $M = 2L + 1$ is the size of the kernel, defined by $\mathbf{K}_B = \text{sgn}(k) \cdot \text{sgn}(l) \forall k, l \in [-L, L]$, where sgn is the sign function. This yields a novelty function $\Delta_{\text{kernel}}(n)$ for each index $n \in [1 : d]$ of \mathbf{X} as follows:

$$\Delta_{\text{kernel}}(n) = \sum_{k, l \in [-L, L]} \mathbf{K}(k, l) \cdot \mathbf{S}(n + k, n + l) \quad (3.2)$$

Figure 3.2: Example of Harmonic SSM resulting from the application of Equation 3.1 on the TPS signal of “Crazy Little Things Called Love” by Queen, using a sampling rate $f_s = 1$. Four main block-like structures are visible, correlating with the musical form of the piece. Smaller, nested harmonic structures of lower granularity are observed within these blocks.

for $n \in [L + 1 : d - L]$. When \mathbf{K} is located within a relatively uniform region of \mathbf{S} , the positive and negative values of the product tend to sum to zero (small novelty). Conversely, when \mathbf{K} is at the crux of a checkerboard-like structure of \mathbf{S} , the values of the product are all positive and sum up to a large value (high novelty) [101].

Local maxima of the novelty curve are then used to detect the boundaries of neighbouring segments that correspond to contrasting harmonic parts. For this, we use a peak peaking method that applies a smoothing filter to the novelty function (to reduce the effect of noise-like fluctuations) and uses adaptive thresholding to select a peak when novelty exceeds a local average [102]. Segment boundaries are then used to split \mathbf{X} and the corresponding \mathbf{q} into a number of non-overlapping harmonic structures. This yields $\bar{\mathbf{q}} = \bar{\mathbf{q}}^1, \dots, \bar{\mathbf{q}}^P$, where P denotes the number of structures.

Linking harmonic segments via similarity

Each harmonic structure $\bar{\mathbf{q}}^i$ is then considered for harmonic similarity. Since $\bar{\mathbf{q}}^i$ is still a time series (a partition of \mathbf{q} , the Harmonic Profile), we formulate the harmonic similarity between two harmonic structures by comparing their time series. This is done using Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) – an algorithm for comparing time series, which has been widely used across various domains, including speech recognition [103], pattern recognition [104], and bioinformatics [105]. DTW has desirable properties, as it is invariant to time shifts, and robust to local variations.

Vanilla DTW compares two time series by calculating the cumulative distances between each point/observation. It allows for non-linear alignment between the time series by considering the local warping path. The cost matrix, holding the cumulative distance between each corresponding point, is constructed using the Euclidean distance:

$$d_{DTW}(\bar{\mathbf{q}}^i, \bar{\mathbf{p}}^j) = \sqrt{\sum_{(v,w) \in \pi} \|\bar{q}_v^i + \bar{p}_w^j\|^2} \quad (3.3)$$

Figure 3.3: Illustration of the *Harmory Ontology* using the Grafoo notation as in Chapter 2.

where π is the optimal warping path – the shortest cumulative distance between the time series (found via dynamic programming). As the computational complexity of vanilla DTW is quadratic in the sequence length, here we use the *Sakoe-Chiba* variant. The latter achieves linear complexity $\mathcal{O}(N \cdot w)$, by constraining the warping path within a window of size w , rather than using all points (N).

Prior to the computation of similarities, time series are normalised and resampled to meet the same length, and standardised to zero mean and unit variance. This has the effect of comparing time series by looking at their shapes in an amplitude-invariant manner – which brings us closer to the identification of harmonic patterns.

The latter emerge after retrieving the k most similar structures for each segment \bar{q}^i , and applying a filtration to retain only those structures \bar{p}^j whose $d_{DTW}(\bar{q}^i, \bar{p}^j)$ is below a given threshold. Structures sharing the same (normalised) TPS time series ($d_{DTW} = 0$) define a distinct harmonic pattern; whereas segments with similar time series can be grouped within the same pattern family/cluster.

Harmory KG creation

An ontology, called *Harmory Ontology*, was developed for the creation of the Knowledge Graph (KG). The ontology directly re-uses the Core ontology from PON and is compliant to our modules for representing musical content (Music Projection, Representation). This allows to link Harmory to ChoCo³ [87]. For each piece, the ontology allows to: (i) store its metadata, such as title, genre, and artist; (ii) hold the harmonic segmentation (see Section 3.1.1); and (iii) relate similar segments (see Section 3.1.1). This enables semantic access to the aforementioned data via SPARQL.

The model is illustrated in Figure 3.3, using the Grafoo notation⁴. A piece of music is expressed by means of the class `har:MusicalWork`, which corresponds to the `mm:MusicEntity` in the Music Meta Ontology. The metadata of a work is stored via `core:hasTitle`, `core:hasGenre`, and `core:hasArtist`, which describe the title, musical genre and composer or performer of the piece, respectively. Here, these relations are intended as binary relationships streamlining the use of Music Meta for this particular application (due to the lack of granular metadata).

A musical work has a `har:SegmentationSituation` – a specialisation of the *Situation Pattern* [106] describing a segmentation performed by a specific `har:SegmentationAlgorithm` that produces one or more `har:Segments`. In this context, a harmonic sequence is split/partitioned into a number of segments, with their

³ChoCo SPARQL endpoint: <https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/choco/sparql>

⁴Grafoo Notation: <https://essepuntato.it/graffoo/>

ordering allowing for reconstruction. Each sequence also holds its chords, using the class `mf:Chord`. Each segment is linked to its corresponding `har:SegmentPattern` – an abstraction of the TPS pattern normalised on the temporal axis. Hence, several `har:Patterns` may have the same `har:SegmentPattern`. Similarity relations are expressed via the class `har:SegmentPatternSimilarity`, which relates two Segment Patterns and holds their similarity value via the datatype property `har:hasSimilarityValue`.

A full evaluation of the workflow – focused on the harmonic segmentation and similarity method, is given in [107]. Examples of uses of Harmony for computational creativity are provided in Section 3.4.

3.1.2 Tonalities: modelling theoretical concepts for analysis

The Tonalities KG includes data⁵ from 377 MEI scores and their annotations w.r.t. theoretical concepts (roots, harmonic progressions, dissonant patterns, cadences, etc.), using the 2 theoretical models in the `Music Analysis` module. A schematic representation of the analytical process annotation for a cadence in a composition from the modal period (Renaissance) is illustrated in Figure 3.4. This representation shows all the logical steps and analytical components (= Analytical Entities, following the Cidoc CRM vocabulary) that are needed to correctly describe a cadence: a group of six notes are selected (see the yellow rectangle on the left); all the six notes globally compose the cadence, that belongs to two different typologies of cadences as described in the theoretical models (= Cadence type A, and Cadence type B); two of the six notes can be classified as a melodic clausula (= Bassizans); one of these two notes is indicated by the analyst as being the penultimate note (= Penultima) of the melodic clausula. Moreover, a specific KG also contains data about the bibliographic contexts of the annotated works, such as composers and different editions of the same work. Next steps in the forthcoming months are: i) working on the second version of the interface (improving ergonomics, reducing time-consuming procedures, developing the comparative section where analysts can exchange opinions and confront on controversial aspects); ii) implementing new theoretical models within the `Music Analysis` module; iii) adding new corpora of scores suggested or encouraged by musicologists and music analysts (one on cadences in Lully's operatic output).

3.1.3 Tunes: building a KG of orally transmitted melodies

The TUNES knowledge graph contains data about melodies that have been in oral circulation in Europe spanning a time period of almost 500 years. The KG combines metadata and similarity data, enabling the retrieval of historical variants of melodies. The current version of the KG⁶ is based on an ad hoc vocabulary and contains data from four large collections of songs:

- Ceol Rince na hÉireann (CRE) corpus (Irish), c. 1,200 tunes.
- Meertens Tune Collections – MTC-FS-INST-2.0 (Dutch), c. 18,000 tunes.
- ESAC Folksong Databases (mostly German), c. 8,300 tunes.
- The Session Corpus (Irish), more than 40,000 tunes.

The current version of the KG will be replaced with a version that is fully aligned with the Polifonia Ontology Network, mainly using the Music Meta module. This version will also incorporate other major collections of digitized melodies, notably the c. 1.8 million incipits from *Répertoire International des Sources Musicales (RISM)*⁷ and the c. 66 thousand incipits from the *Early American Secular Music and Its European Sources, 1589–1839: An Index*⁸.

From a modeling perspective, the Tunes Knowledge Graph is constructed upon the foundation of the Music Meta framework, adapted for the realm of folk music. This innovative module introduces the notion of “tune families,” categorising tunes through melodic resemblances, supported by in-depth musicological analysis. This methodology seamlessly extends to lyrics families, embracing a comprehensive understanding of musicological intricacies.

⁵<https://data-iremum.huma-num.fr/sparql>

⁶<https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/tunes/sparql>

⁷<https://rism.info>

⁸<https://www.cdss.org/elibrary/Easmes/Index.htm>

Figure 3.4: Example taken from the Tonalities KG for a modal composition from the Renaissance period.

3.1.4 Meetups: a KG of historical encounters between musicians

The MEETUPS Knowledge Graph contains data about historical encounters of people in the musical world in Europe from c. 1800 to c. 1945. All the data is extracted from artists' biographies, mainly from Wikipedia artists' web pages. A total of 33,309 biographies were collected for knowledge extraction and construction of the KG. Currently, the KG contains data extracted from 1012 biographies.

The MEETUPS KG was built focused on identifying the entities that are part of a historical meetup: people, places, time expressions and meetup type. We start by collecting data that provides an overview of music personalities' lives, such as biographies in text format. The entity recognition and disambiguation process is performed at the sentence level. We process the corpus to link entities such as places and people, extracting time expressions and classifying them according to meetup types. The output of this step is a bag of entities at the sentence level, grouped

by paragraphs and sections. We then run the coreference resolution step, which allows to find mentions to people and places. Once the entities are extracted, we run the process to find encounters within the text, at sentence level or on a larger chunk.

Meetups KG describes 3.1K+ historical meetups, mentioning 8.5K+ people from 1.5K+ places in Europe (see Table 3.2). It uses as a framework the MEETUPS Ontology.

Type	Total entities
Meetups	3186
Persons mentioned	8569
Places mentions	1581
Time expressions	4777
Subjects	743
Excerpts	5356

Table 3.2: MEETUPS Knowledge Graph Entities statistics

The KG was constructed using the results of the knowledge extraction process described in [108]. We used SPARQL Anything [109] and the MEETUPS Ontology (see Section 2.2.5) as a framework for building the knowledge graph of historical, the KG is currently published⁹ in Turtle RDF format and can be queried via SPARQL endpoint¹⁰.

The current version of the MEETUPS Knowledge Graph is aligned with the Polifonia Ontology Network, mainly using the `Core` module, and already included in the design of the MEETUPS Ontology. For its final release, the Meetups KG will include the total number of biographies collected.

3.1.5 Bells: mapping the historical landscape of Bells

Bells KG describes 88 bells catalogued by the Italian Ministry of Culture¹¹. It relies on the `Bells` module and is part of the ArCo KG – the largest Italian cultural heritage KG from the Italian General Catalogue of Cultural Heritage. The Bells KG was already presented in D2.3 [56] and is outlined here to report its integration and reuse of PON.

3.1.6 MusicBO: a KG of Bologna’s musical heritage from textual sources

Language	#sent-AMR graph pairs (Text2AMR)	#filtered sent-AMR graph pairs (Automatic metrics evaluation)	#named graphs (AMR2RDF)	#triples
EN	51.814	5.965	5.798	413.060
ITA	10.563	1.815	1.759	118.162
Overall	15.747	7.780	7.557	531.222

Table 3.3: Statistics describing the KG resulting from the application of the text2KG pipeline to MusicBO corpus.

As described in D2.3 [56], MusicBO KG is built via text-to-KG methods [82] on a collection of 137 documents¹² on performances and encounters between musicians, composers, and critics happened in Bologna from the 17th century. As mentioned in Section 2, the KG¹³ is used as input to the *bottom-up* modelling of the `MusicBO` ontology. We provide in Table 3.3 the statistics regarding the text2KG process. The resulting `muBOsic` KG is described in a

⁹Meetups KG repository <https://github.com/polifonia-project/meetups-knowledge-graph/>

¹⁰Meetups KG SPARQL endpoint: <https://data.open.ac.uk/page/context/meetups>

¹¹<https://dati.cultura.gov.it/sparql>

¹²<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6672165>

¹³<https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/musicbo/sparql>

dedicated collection of data stories¹⁴ published in MELODY. Through MELODY, it is possible to visualise the SPARQL queries used to interrogate the muBOsic KG endpoint and build the published stories. The stories offer insights into the characters who played prominent roles in Bologna’s music scene and the most common events and situations involving these characters, thereby revealing Bologna as a key hub for artistic production and music-related activities.

3.2 Adoption by Polifonia Stakeholders

In addition to internal and potential adopters, industrial and institutional stakeholders in the Polifonia Stakeholder Network have also expressed interest to use PON resources. These include the **Digital Music Observatory**, concerning the use of `Music Meta` and `Source` to annotate the numerous music resources of the consortium; and the **Université Catholique de Louvain** where Anne-Emmanuelle Ceulemans uses the `Music Analysis` module for studying the annotation of cadences in Josquin des Prez (composer of High Renaissance music).

We have also planned work with **Deezer**, **Songfacts**, and **MusiciD** for the evaluation, extension, and reuse of `Music Meta` driven by their resources; and collaborations with the EU H2020 **MuseIT**¹⁵ project to extend the ChoCo KG.

One of the tasks in the MuseIT project concerns with the generation of music based on the emotions of an individual experiencing a cultural heritage artefact. In this context, we are exploring collaborative efforts for augmenting the emotions data to the ChoCo KG and implementing a method to generate the music, enabled by Harmory. Another ongoing idea involves learning joint embeddings with chords, structural patterns and the emotions data to map and infer emotional annotations for the tracks in ChoCo in order to derive the desired music.

3.3 Survey on challenges and requirements for music ontologies

To motivate the research gaps and collect potential interest of adoption of PON, we conducted an online survey in which we ask potential adopters 14 questions regarding their background, relevance, and interest in using music ontologies. The survey was conducted via Google Forms, and distributed in the Semantic Web (SW), Music Information Retrieval (MIR), and Digital Humanities mailing lists – gathering a total of $N = 61$ responses.

Among our respondents, 25 work in Semantic Web, 23 in MIR, 26 in Musicology. Most of them have encountered the need for modelling music related data and resources with ontologies (65.6%), focusing primarily on music metadata (45) theory and notation (29), annotations (25) and instruments (28); with 75% doing research or project work related to music data with multiple stakeholders.

Participants were asked to quantify the agreement with statements from 1 (absolutely disagree) to 5 (absolutely agree), 3 being a neutral response (NR; neither agree nor disagree). Results are illustrated in Figure 3.5. From questions 6-14 we found that: 49.2% find the reuse of existing music ontologies to be challenging (with 42.6% NR), and the same can be said about the interoperability of existing ontologies (57%; 36% NR), their lack of coverage of concepts related to music history and music cultural heritage (57.3%; 32.8% NR); and the lack of large datasets of competency questions for this domain (63%; 34% NR). We also find strong evidence for potential reuse of PON, as participants would be interested in using ontologies for music metadata (78.7%), sources (80.3%), musical instruments (70.5%), and music content (57.4%; 21.3% NR), as well as a competency question dataset for musical heritage (65%; 26.7% NR).

¹⁴https://projects.dharc.unibo.it/melody/musicbo/music_in_bologna_knowledge_graph_overview

¹⁵<https://www.muse-it.eu/>

Figure 3.5: Selection of questions 4, 6, 7-14 from the online survey, where responses are expressed on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 5 (*strongly agree*).

3.4 Avenues for computational creativity

Creativity has been defined as the ability to come up with new, surprising, and valuable ideas or artifacts [110]. These can be abstract concepts, scientific theories, solutions to real-world problems, but also new designs and artworks. In particular, combinational creativity has been defined as a form of creativity where the creation of new ideas results from the combination of familiar ones [110].

In the music domain, data-driven generative systems based on deep learning methods have achieved impressive results on symbolic music [111], and they can also produce realistic outputs when trained on the raw audio [112]. The variety of computationally creative methods for music is quite broad and diversified, and has already enabled the exploration of novel forms of artistic co-creation [113]. These range from the automatic generation, completion, and alteration of chord progressions and melodies, to the creation of mashups, and audio snippets from textual prompts [114]. Due to their success, some of these systems have already been integrated into commercial software, such as *Aiva*¹⁶ and *Amper*¹⁷ – allowing users to generate full music pieces based on their desiderata.

In this section, we describe potential applications of Harmory (Section 3.1.1) across different tasks and use cases for computational creativity. Compared to data-driven solutions, we do not aim at improving the state of the art in music generation, but rather to provide a transparent system to support creative workflows [115] by leveraging our Music Knowledge Graphs.

Here, we show examples of trustworthy applications for pattern discovery, human-machine chord generation, and harmonic similarity. The latter is more of musicological interest, whereas the former are both creative use cases. Each application is demonstrated through a set of *Prompts*, expressed in natural language, which correspond to SPARQL query templates to interrogate Harmory. The latter are fully available on our repository¹⁸.

3.4.1 Pattern discovery

The traversal of the Harmonic Memory makes it possible to obtain granular information of the harmonic structure of songs. In particular, it is possible to explore the harmonic segments of each song, the patterns related to each segment, and the similarities with other patterns/segments found in other pieces.

A composer may start with a harmonic pattern in mind, and initiate a creative exploration of the KG by leveraging music and metadata.

Prompt 1 *For a given pattern, which are the tracks (titles, artists and genres) in which the pattern can be found?*

Prompt 2 *Given a music genre, what are the most frequent patterns?*

To support creative exploration, more complex prompts can be formulated in order to narrow down the search, and eventually discover surprising or unexpected outputs, if present.

Prompt 3 *Which harmonic patterns are used in “Michelle” by The Beatles, but also in a classical composition?*

Prompt 4 *Which patterns used by The Beatles in “Michelle” but not in “Hey Jude” contain at least a B flat major seventh chord?*

In the Harmory KG, we have also included known patterns, which are labelled in such a way as to indicate their origin, mood, or harmonic function within the progression. These labelled harmonic fragments can be used as input for a query, e.g. for searching songs that contain them:

Prompt 5 *Which tracks include a dominant cycle in seven steps?*

¹⁶<https://www.aiva.ai>

¹⁷<https://www.ampermusic.com>

¹⁸SPARQL queries: <https://github.com/smashub/harmory/tree/main/queries>

Figure 3.6: Example of a generated chord progression using a pattern-based prompt. Given a first segment, each segment is chosen according to similarity to the subsequent one in the original sequence, and filtered according to arbitrary criteria. The second segment is taken from a song that has “hip-hop” as genre, while the next two segments are chosen by *artist*.

3.4.2 Human-machine chord generation

Harmory also enables combinational creativity use cases. New progressions are generated by moving across patterns through temporal and similarity links, based on the given creative requirements. At generation time, this has the advantage of giving recognition to all artists that contributed to the new creation, as shown in Figure 3.6.

First, it can provide statistical information regarding variations of a given harmonic sequence. As these variations come from real pieces, it is also possible to leverage metadata for controlling the generation. To do this, a prompt can be formulated from a given (possibly new) harmonic sequence (or a part of it), to retrieve all the all harmonic sequences using the same pattern.

Prompt 6 *Given a chord sequence, which are its variations, and which tracks these variations belong to?*

Similarly, it is also possible to query the most similar (or most distant) harmonic sequences to a given one:

Prompt 7 *Given a chord sequence, which are its most similar chord sequences, sorted by similarity?*

These simple constructs already allow to generate new harmonic sequences, starting from either a known harmonic idea/pattern, or a full progression. If starting from a full progression, one way is to identify the first harmonic segment that makes it up. From this point, transitions can be made using *similarity relations*, while taking into account the order of the different segments (*temporal connections*) and their tonality. For example, starting from the first harmonic segment of a song (a priming sequence), one can then generate a continuation by identifying similar sequences to the next sequence, filtering them by tonality (or/and by artist, genre, title) and repeat this process recursively for a number of steps, criteria, or with the supervision/control of the user.

Prompt 8 *Create a progression starting with “Michelle” by The Beatles, continuing with a segment found in a classical piece of music, and then continuing with another by Chet Baker.*

3.4.3 Harmonic similarity

From a musicological perspective, the KG can also be used to analyse similarity relations between tracks – by leveraging the local information relating harmonic structures. This also allows for the formal definition of similarity functions (depending on a genre- or task- specific notions) by using logical operators (SPARQL syntax) over harmonic segments/patterns. An example is given below.

Prompt 9 *Given a track, which tracks contain patterns with a distance of less than 0.2, each having the same order?*

As expected, the results of this query are almost exclusively cover songs of the given track. Nevertheless, a similarity function can be defined to be less strict, and hence more explorative. For instance, the similarity function below uses a higher similarity threshold for patterns, and does not constrain on the order of segments.

Prompt 10 *Given a track, which tracks contain patterns with a distance of less than 0.5, regardless of their order?*

4 Conclusions

This deliverable mainly focuses on the creation of the Polifonia Ontology Network (PON), a collection of *expressive* ontologies for musical cultural heritage that enable *interoperability* of existent semantic models for music content and contexts (MusicOWL, Music Notation, Music Ontology, DOREMUS, etc.). Departing from multidisciplinary and domain-expert based requirements in the Polifonia project, we applied and extended the XD methodology for ontology engineering both methodologically (persona/story framework for the collection of requirements) and technologically (IDEA framework for NLP-assisted co-design). We released 15 new ontologies in PON (v1.0) and the PolifoniaCQ dataset of 361 competency questions under [CC-BY 4.0](#); together with documentations, data examples, and SPARQL queries for each module. Our pilots have already started reusing PON to create Music KGs ranging from chord annotations, harmonic similarity and pattern extraction to music analysis, historical instruments, and musical encounters. In addition, we provide strong evidence of current and potential reuse by institutional and industrial stakeholders, as well as opportunities for using our contributions for computational creativity.

We are currently performing an extensive CQ-driven evaluation of PON modules (whose results will be covered in D2.8), and iteratively improving our ontology modules based on the experience of reuse from our pilots. These activities are complemented by the extension and the revision of Music Meta (the PON ontology dealing with music metadata) driven by the collaborations with our industrial and cultural heritage stakeholders. More precisely, our work with Deezer is testing the coverage and the expressiveness of Music Meta to model music industry metadata, and the potential reuse of the resulting KGs for addressing metadata attribution; whereas the collaboration with the Digital Music Observatory is focusing on the reuse of our ontologies for licensing and copyright management.

Overall, the maintenance of PON requires the creation of documentation and software resources that can facilitate the understanding of our work and the creation of a community of contributors around our repositories. We found this to be a fundamental step for the reuse of our outputs within and beyond Polifonia. To address this, we have recently started leveraging Language Models for the automatic curation of such material depending on the level of familiarity of potential users. We are also committed to disseminate our outputs in the Music Information Retrieval and Semantic Web communities, as we will present our work at the the 24th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference (ISMIR) [65], and at the 22nd International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC) [57]; instead, Harmory was disseminated at the WebConference, Texas (US) [55]. In relation to the aforementioned considerations on documentation and potential reuse, we also plan to run tutorials and seminars to disseminate PON, and use our resources for educational purpose in Semantic Web, Network Data Analysis, and Music Technology courses.

5 Compliance to the FAIR principles

The following outputs have been released as a result of the work described in this deliverable:

- The Polifonia Ontology Network (PON) v1.0, which comprehends 15 music ontologies, bringing interoperability with current works and driven by the diverse requirements and expertise in the Polifonia project.
- The PolifoniaCQ dataset, a collection of 361 competency questions for music cultural heritage.
- The IDEA framework, a family of NLP tools supporting the extension of the XD methodology for collaborative human-AI ontology engineering.
- The KGs deployed by our pilots, and in particular, the Harmory KG – providing harmonic patterns and their connection using state of the art methods and software for harmonic segmentation and similarity.
- A survey on the current challenges and issues of music ontologies, which has motivated this work and also allowed to collect evidence of potential reuse of PON.

This section encompasses information which helps to the knowledge management in the project and to make Polifonia FAIR (operating according to principles of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This ensures compliance with the guidelines and principles of the Polifonia Data Management Plan (v2.0) [116]. We remind the Polifonia 10 Rules for Open Science from D7.2 [116] as follows.

- R1: Polifonia requires that all essential components of the Polifonia Ecosystem are registered in the Polifonia Github community.
- R2: Polifonia recommends to use Zenodo to register output.
- R3: Organise access to your resources via the Polifonia Portal/Polifonia server.
- R4: Use your ORCID to identify you as an author!
- R5: Acknowledge the grant (the Polifonia project) with each output!
- R6: Use DOI's to refer to work you produce!
- R7: For datasets you think are important cornerstones of your work deposit them into the Polifonia Ecosystem (see R1). Consider archiving 'authoritative versions' into a certified data repository!
- R8: Authorship/publication Netiquette
- R9: R9: Adhere FAIR principles and licencing principles
- R10: If in doubt: Ask the DataManagers of your institutions and consult the DataStewards of Polifonia.

5.1 Polifonia Ontology Network – Data

Requirement	Options	Outcome
Polifonia 10 Rules	None, R1, R2, ... , R10	R1, R2, R3, R4, R5, R6, R7, R8, R9 (see Table 2.1)
GitHub link	None, Link	https://github.com/polifonia-project/ontology-network
Zenodo link	None, Link	https://zenodo.org/badge/latest/doi/10.5281/zenodo.372536364
Ecosystem integration	Yes, Planned, N/A	Yes, see https://github.com/polifonia-project/pon-template
PON Alignment	Full, Partial, Planned, N/A	Full
License	License	CC-BY-4.0 (all modules)
Deployment link	Link, N/A, Planned	https://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/ontology-network/

Table 5.1: Overview of FAIRness coverage for PON

We have implemented a number of actions to ensure that these outputs are in compliance with the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship [117]. In particular, for PON, all code, data, and related resources are available online at <https://github.com/polifonia-project/ontology-network/tree/main>, Both the latest versions of PON are available on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/badge/latestdoi/372536364>), in synchronisation with GitHub releases at <https://github.com/polifonia-project/ontology-network/releases> for consistent versioning. Via GitHub and Zenodo, PON project has a unique and persistent identifier and is registered in a searchable source. Through the addition of YAML metadata according to the Polifonia Ecosystem rulebook¹, all modules in PON are also integrated within the Ecosystem automatically through its future releases with well-described, machine-processable metadata from various interoperable schemas. Furthermore, being integrated as part of the Polifonia Ecosystem, all data and metadata produced use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation. The same applies to the aforementioned contributions, whose links to the corresponding resources were given in the previous sections.

Annotations in PON. Global annotation properties have been integrated into the OWL file of each ontology in PON. These include the following information: description, licence, version, creator(s), maintainer(s), preferred namespace, and so forth (see Listing 5.1 for an example). The annotation properties provide documentation at level of each ontology module, and also contribute to their findability from ontology portals. Indeed, most properties were chosen to make PON modules compliant with the *Linked Open Vocabularies* (LOV, <https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/>). Through their lookup service, PON classes and properties will be easily searchable and findable to promote the reuse of our contributions outside Polifonia.

Listing 5.1: Example of ontology annotations in PON modules (Music Meta)

```

...
<xml></xml>
  <owl:Ontology rdf:about="https://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/music-meta">
    <owl:versionIRI rdf:resource="https://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/music-meta/1.0"/>
    <owl:imports rdf:resource="https://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/core/0.1"/>
    <dc:creator xml:lang="en">Andrea Poltronieri </dc:creator >
    <dc:creator xml:lang="en">Jacopo de Berardinis </dc:creator >
    <dc:creator xml:lang="en">Nicolas Lazzari </dc:creator >
    <dc:creator xml:lang="en">Valentina Carriero </dc:creator >
    <dc:creator xml:lang="en">Valentina Presutti </dc:creator >
    <dc:license rdf:resource="https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0"/>
    <terms:license rdf:resource="https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0"/>
    <cc:license rdf:resource="https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0"/>
    <rdfs:comment xml:lang="en">The Music Meta ontology is a rich ... </rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label xml:lang="en">Music Meta Ontology </rdfs:label >
    <dc:title xml:lang="en">Music Meta Ontology </dc:title >
    <dc:description xml:lang="en">The Music Meta ontology is a rich ... </dc:description >
    <owl:versionInfo xml:lang="en">1.0 </owl:versionInfo >
    <terms:modified>"2023-07-17"^^xsd:date </terms:modified >
    <terms:issued>"2023-04-12"^^xsd:date </terms:issued >
    <vann:preferredNamespacePrefix>mm: </vann:preferredNamespacePrefix >
    <vann:preferredNamespaceUri>https://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/music-meta/ </vann:preferredNamespaceUri >
  </owl:Ontology >
...

```

¹<https://github.com/polifonia-project/rulebook>

Universal Resource Identifiers (URIs). For the Polifonia Ontology Network, the namespaces were introduced in Section 2. These are permanent URIs that were created with the W3C Permanent Identifier Community Group². The process is achieved through registering redirect rule from their central GitHub repository, which has been forked within the Polifonia organisation to handle pull request to the former repository³.

Licensing. All the outputs presented in this deliverable follow the guidelines and the recommendations in the Polifonia Data Management Plan. PON ontologies, the PolifoniaCQ dataset, and the Knowledge Graphs contributed in this document are made available under CC-BY 4.0. An exception here is the Harmory Knowledge Graph, which is released as derivative work of ChoCo – whose license has been extensively covered in D1.5 [92] and [87]. Hence, the Harmory KG follows the same licensing strategy of ChoCo; whereas the software underpinning its creation (harmonic segmentation, similarity, and data transformation) is released under the MIT license. Finally, the IDEA framework is released as an open source Python project, and follows with an ISC license⁴.

Sustainability and preservation plan. PON is under version control on public GitHub repositories (c.f. Table 2.1), and all repositories are also published on Zenodo (with associated DOIs). The storage of all resources on GitHub guarantees their persistence beyond the project, with the University of Bologna and the Italian Ministry of Culture (MiC) committed to host and maintain PON on a long term basis. We also remark that PON is reused as a sibling ontology project of ArCo by MiC.

On limiting bias. Limiting bias in the creation of ontology and Knowledge Graphs is an open challenge. We recall that our mitigation strategy for PON includes: 1) involving domain expert, such as musicologists, analysts, musicians and historians from different institutions and background (providing complementary views and perspectives); 2) addressing the requirements of the 10 pilots in the Polifonia project (which provide reasonable diversity of application domains), and 3) generalising over the resulting requirements by identifying common concepts, and again, validating ontologies with our experts. A notable example is the Music Meta module, which has been receiving constant supervision by our heterogeneous and complementary pool of music experts, and is now under refinement and extension thanks with our stakeholders (c.f. Section 3).

Documentation. While improving and extending our contributions, we have also invested efforts on producing high quality documentation for our resources. In addition to the Ecosystem annotations discussed before, two further strategies are being put into place. First, the ontology design team has been producing documentation, examples and tutorials on a website specifically dedicated to PON: <https://polifonia-project.github.io/ontology-network/>⁵. Furthermore, each ontology module in PON follows a specific template on GitHub – which is in line with the guidelines introduced in D2.3 [56]. To implement such guidelines, a template repository for PON ontologies has been created at <https://github.com/polifonia-project/pon-template>, together with a checklist to evaluate their adoption⁶. This ensures that each PON module provides the following information.

- A clear and well-structured README where all the preliminary information that are necessary to understand the domain and the goals of the ontology are provided upfront.
- DOI, license, URI, and link to further documentation are provided in the header.
- Graffoo diagrams of (at least) the main elements of design of the ontology.
- The competency questions that the ontology addresses (or plans to address) in a tabular format.
- A template of the Ecosystem header, which is reused consistently for all the ontologies in PON.
- A template of the OWL ontology specifying the annotation properties outlined before (c.f. Listing 5.1).
- Examples of SPARQL queries, possibly addressing the outlined competency questions.
- Various statistics (no. of classes, data property, etc.), reused ontologies, and datasets using the resource.

²<https://w3id.org>

³<https://github.com/polifonia-project/w3id.org>

⁴<https://opensource.org/licenses/isc-license-txt/>

⁵The website does not yet appear in the Polifonia Ecosystem, and the corresponding annotation is under development for a more consistent integration with other outputs of the project.

⁶<https://github.com/polifonia-project/pon-template/blob/main/checklist.md>

The screenshot shows the 'Create a Music Entity' page on the Polifonia Ontology Network website. The page includes a navigation menu on the left with options like 'Welcome', 'Notation primer', 'Music Meta', 'Getting started', 'Create an Artist', 'Create a Music Entity', 'Create a Performance', 'Links and provenance', 'Congratulations!', 'Advanced guide', 'Music Representation', 'Music Projection', 'Music Algorithm', and 'CoMeta'. The main content area has a breadcrumb trail: 'Music Meta > Getting started > Create a Music Entity'. The title is 'Create a Music Entity'. The text explains that the focal point is the `mm:MusicEntity` class, which is an Information Object composed of elements like `mm:Text`, `mm:Libretto`, `mm:CompositionObject`, and `mm:Instrumentation`. A diagram shows the class hierarchy and relationships, including `mm:MusicEntity` as a subclass of `mm:InformationObject` and `mm:MusicEntity` as a subclass of `mm:MusicEntity`. The diagram also shows relationships like `mm:hasPart`, `mm:hasText`, `mm:hasInstrumentation`, and `mm:hasScore`. A legend on the right lists various classes and their relationships.

A `mm:CompositionObject` describes the form of the composition (`mm:FormType`), its constituents parts (e.g. `mm:Movement` or `mm:Section`), and its key (`mm:Key`). In addition, its datatype properties describe the tempo of the composition (`mm:tempo`) and its order (`mm:orderNumber`). A `mm:Instrumentation` can instead be formalised in a `mm:Score`, which can be either digital or paper. Through the score, the instrumentation describes one or more `mm:MediumOfPerformance`, each of which has a cardinality (e.g. 3 violins).

Figure 5.1: A screenshot of the PON website, providing documentation and tutorials for reusing our ontologies.

Notably, documentation and diagrams are synchronised with the PON website, to achieve consistency and minimise redundancy across our artifacts.

5.2 PolifoniaCQ dataset – Data

Requirement	Options	Outcome
Polifonia 10 Rules	None, R1, R2, ... , R10	R1, R2, R3, R4, R5, R6, R7, R8, R9
GitHub link	None, Link	https://github.com/polifonia-project/polifoniacq-dataset
Zenodo link	None, Link	https://zenodo.org/badge/latest/doi/372536364
Ecosystem integration	Yes, Planned, N/A	Yes
PON Alignment	Full, Partial, Planned, N/A	N/A
License	License	CC-BY-4.0
Deployment link	Link, N/A, Planned	Served through GitHub

Table 5.2: FAIRness coverage for the PolifoniaCQ dataset according to D7.2

5.3 Harmory KG – Data

Requirement	Options	Outcome
Polifonia 10 Rules	None, R1, R2, ... , R10	R1, R2, R3, R4, R5, R6, R7, R8, R9
GitHub link	None, Link	https://github.com/smashub/harmory
Zenodo link	None, Link	https://zenodo.org/record/8021211
Ecosystem integration	Yes, Planned, N/A	Yes
PON Alignment	Full, Partial, Planned, N/A	Partial, Planned for full alignment
License	License	CC-BY-4.0
Deployment link	Link, N/A, Planned	Served through GitHub

Table 5.3: FAIRness coverage for the Harmory KG.

5.4 IDEA Framework – Software

Requirement	Options	Outcome
Polifonia 10 Rules	None, R1, R2, ... , R10	R1, R2, R4, R5, R6, R8, R9
GitHub link	None, Link	https://github.com/polifonia-project/idea
Zenodo link	None, Link	https://zenodo.org/badge/latestdoi/372536364
Ecosystem integration	Yes, Planned, N/A	Planned
PON Alignment	Full, Partial, Planned, N/A	N/A
License	License	CC-BY-4.0
Deployment link	Link, N/A, Planned	https://polifonia-project.github.io/idea/

Table 5.4: FAIRness coverage for the IDEA framework.

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